

CommuniCity

Innovative Solutions Responding
to the Needs of Cities & Communities

D2.4 Guidelines for translating for marginalised and vulnerable communities- final version

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CommuniCity

D2.4 Guidelines for translating for marginalised and vulnerable communities – final version

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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to provide guidelines for translations for co-creation in technology development with marginalised communities. Guidelines can take different forms: they can describe best practices, provide material to be used to improve existing processes or to initiate new ones; or they can acknowledge and highlight challenges, identify problematic choices, envision alternative paths, so that the next iteration can go further than what was explored so far. The goal of the CommuniCity project has been a very ambitious one: to develop models of technology innovation and co-creation together with marginalised communities. There are no generally applicable, viable processes of technology-related and technology-based interventions empowering marginalised communities. CommuniCity is an attempt to learn in this uncharted space, and as to be expected in risky endeavours, the most important lessons are in what did not work as wished or expected, and in what incrementally, along the way, and by design or chance, turned out to improve in general and scalable ways. Work package 2 of CommuniCity tried to capture these learnings, and to translate them into guidelines.

Based on data collected through surveys embedded in the piloting process within CommuniCity, as well as various qualitative data collection methods employed by research partners involved in WP2, co-creation processes utilized in the project were analysed. This analysis suggests that the current piloting process, defined as the CommuniCity Agile Piloting Process, enables and supports certain forms of co-creation, while allowing- only in several cases- some other forms. This likely stems from the inherent features of the CommuniCity piloting model that centres city-led and tech-driven innovation through a time and budget limited frame for piloting.

The deliverable acknowledges that the Agile Piloting process achieves its ambitious goals through an accelerated piloting process. This process demonstrated agility and capacity for incremental learning and for supporting co-creation *"for"* and to some extent *"with"* communities. However, co-creation *"by" communities*, which entails a leading role of communities in the technology and innovation and co-creation processes, shared ownership and decision making, was achieved with the current model only in a selected number of cases in the final piloting round.

Analysis of the entire CommuniCity project as a process shows that critical reflection and knowledge feedback loops between different types of partners, including academic

researchers engaged in the WP2, embedded by-design in the CommuniCity project, deepen the understanding of the concept of “co-creation” within marginalized communities. Furthermore, reflection practice and lessons from the on-the-ground piloting experiences indicate directions for future improvements. The selected piloting process was accommodating various co-creation practices in different cities but leaving somewhat confined space for reimagination and rethinking of more impactful co-creation activities led by communities.

To maintain the model’s agility while enhancing its learning capacities, future applications should not forget to incorporate independent, reflective, creative and open research and collaboration by-design, ensuring that ideation, creation and application of technology involve all stakeholders. In particular, the “*by community*” co-creation model of innovation translates to a community-driven model, revolving around transparency, trust, accountability, joint ownership, public value and oversight, and balancing efficiency with purposeful technological city innovation. Such models are still under development and awaiting full implementation. The document drafts several practical guidelines that could bring technological innovation within marginalised communities closer to this model.

The final draft of this deliverable has been reviewed by the Ethics Board through meetings and written feedback, and their input has been incorporated into the final version.

1. Introduction

The process of digital transformation and innovation has emerged as a critical imperative in contemporary society. Economic competitiveness, alongside the necessity to address multifaceted social challenges, frequently underpins the urgency of rapid digitization. The technological innovations occurring within smart cities represent a complex multi-stakeholder operation that encompasses city governments, technology companies, academic institutions, and civil society organizations. Building on previous initiatives such as Organicity and Synchronicity, which primarily concentrated on the development of Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure and technical advancements in the urban environments, the CommuniCity project shifts its focus toward digital innovations aimed at marginalised communities. This project underscores the significance of co-creation as a vital instrument for fostering inclusion and democratizing the digital transformation process. In this context, CommuniCity stands out as a distinctive project that has engaged 19 cities across Europe with the final result in developing 101 technological pilot initiatives tailored to the needs of marginalised communities.

The present report is grounded in qualitative research that investigates knowledge and learnings about co-creation developed throughout the CommuniCity project, as a base for guidelines for translating co-creation for marginalised and vulnerable communities. In chapter 1, the document gives an overview of the knowledge on co-creation seen through the deliverables of WP2, and in that sense it represents a presentation of artefacts produced throughout the project in this work package. Furthermore, in the same chapter, the document analyses data collected in the surveys with tech-developers as pilot leaders during the CommuniCity piloting processes. This chapter also contains insights obtained from the analysis of the Agile piloting process in relation to the typology of co-creation within marginalised communities marked as co-creation “for- with- by”. Finally, this chapter distinguishes the cases of good practices of co-creation that managed to get closer to the community-led innovation. Empirical analysis is followed by literature review on concepts such as co-creation and participation, Agile piloting and ownership in chapter 3. The document ends with the consolidation of findings and recommendations for future research in the last chapter .

2. Learnings on Co-creation in CommuniCity

Rationale

The deliverable D2.4 Guidelines for Translating Frameworks, Methods, Tools and Principles of Local Innovations for Marginalised and Vulnerable Communities- Final Version contains the consolidated learning on engagement and co-creation. This deliverable collects all results of the WP2- tools, methods, models, principles and frameworks encompassed in nine deliverables D2.1 to D2.9. Common denominator for all deliverables of the WP2 is the quest for pausing and reflection in the speedy processes of technological innovation. These deliverables offer concrete tools for reflection in all phases of this process. Intentionally creating reflection-spots throughout innovation processes and embedding them in the processes by-design, could ensure knowledges of all participants in the process are heard and included. This is specifically relevant in the case of marginalised communities. Furthermore, the new co-creation methods proposed in deliverables D2.3 (Design Justice framework) and D2.7 (The Cloud Weaving Model) conceptualize the role of the tech designer as a community organizer in a potential future model for impactful innovation originating from marginalised communities. Community organising refers to a process in which members of a community come together to take collective action on social issues that impact them all, often requiring facilitation and support. Community facilitation is a specific (often professionalised) skill and can rarely be provided by tech developers (or other stakeholders), unless it is an additional skill they possess. Fundamentals of this idea of bottom-up community organising were translated and communicated to the Agile piloting process led by WP3 and WP5 partners and resulting with incremental learnings on co-creation throughout three rounds of piloting. Traces of community-cantered co-creation have been observed in the selected cases of pilots from Amsterdam, Helsinki, Manchester and Porto and presented in this deliverable.

Knowledge built in previous projects like SynchroniCity and OrganiCity, and other projects of individual beneficiaries (i.e. Forum Virium Helsinki and their Agile piloting process developed in 2019), was brought to CommuniCity in the form of both tacit and

procedural knowledge (models, frameworks, tools, etc.). Throughout the project, WP2 has researched processes of WP3 and WP5 through various qualitative methods (observation, interviews, surveys) combined with literature and document research. Knowledge produced in all deliverables of WP2 was continuously communicated through regular feedback loops (meetings of WP3/5 where WP2 lead was present, as well by participation of AMS as a lead piloting city from WP3/5 in regular bi-weekly WP2 meetings.

First set of guidelines for translation of previous process knowledge into context of marginalised communities was presented in the deliverable D2.1, highlighted the following:

Community translation and co-creation activities, although challenging, offer unique opportunities for experimentation and learning but require careful ethical consideration. Ensuring ‘do no harm,’ maintaining honest communication, addressing power imbalances, and empowering communities from the outset are essential principles guiding respectful and effective engagement.

In the early stages of the project, following the initial round of pilots, deliverable D2.2 significantly contributed to the translation process by broadening the range of available tools. It specifically outlined co-creation methods and offered guidance tailored to marginalised communities. Design justice framework that has been introduced in the deliverable D2.3, and the table with list of critical questions for assessment of design processes (pages 36, 37, 38), encompass five principles of scaling-down as defined by Myerson¹:

1) Cultivate a Participatory Mindset—Not an Expert One: Designer as a community organiser, according to Sasha Costanza-Chock, an author of Design Justice book, is the most suitable position when designing with marginalised communities. A community organizer is deeply immersed in the community, not a parachute that appears suddenly for a short period of time and disappears afterwards. The community organizer is familiar with the challenges of the community, and the community trusts him/her. This conceptualisation is entwined in two deliverables of WP2- D2.3 and D2.7. D2.3 introduces

¹ Jeremy Myerson, Scaling Down: Why Designers Need to Reverse Their Thinking, She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation, Volume 2, Issue 4, 2016, Pages 288–299, ISSN 2405–8726, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2017.06.001>.

the design justice principles for co-creation with marginalised communities, and D2.7 goes further abstracting it on the level of metaphor that compares community organising as tech development with marginalised communities as difficult as “cloud weaving”. To facilitate reflection and stimulate imagination, this speculative model is visualised in the form of hand-drawn cards. In this way the second principle of scaling-down is addressed- **2) Make the Process Design-Infused—Not Design-Led.** Furthermore, this principle is addressed by the deliverable D2.9 where principles for ethical co-creation in practice were an inspiration for development of a visual tool for reflection during co-creation processes- A Co-Creation Reboot CardSet developed by AUAS. **3) Design for People—Not Personas.** The third principle of scaling-down is addressed by the deliverable D2.2 which has introduced an exhaustive list of co-creation methods and tips for co-creation with marginalised communities. They focus on engaging people from marginalised communities through creative and empathy-led methods. **4) Aim for Engagement—Not Abstraction.** This principle is encompassed in deliverables D2.6 and D2.4 which are reflecting on practical insights from CommuniCity pilots and the Agile piloting process, giving concrete recommendations to enable genuine engagement with the marginalised communities. **5) Build on Assets—Don’t Just Minimize Deficits.** Several cases of best practices of CommuniCity pilots presented in this deliverable, illustrates how piloting and co-creation processes empowered involved communities, but also tech developers, resulting in examples of genuine collaboration and co-ownership. In these cases, members of marginalised communities are not seen through their individual lack, but from the strength and interconnectedness of their communities.

The guidelines for translating frameworks, methods, tools and principles of local innovations for marginalised and vulnerable communities are encompassed in all deliverables of WP2, from D2.1 to D2.9, forming a base for various dimensions within CommuniCity such as: **Alignment:** the principles of ethical engagement (D2.8 and D2.9) and ethical framework (D2.5 and D2.6) align processes in CommuniCity with community values and European standards. **Regulation:** Guidelines for compliances with current regulations, especially the AI Act are provided through several instances in the CommuniCity project- in the WP1, through the Ethics Board Report D1.2, as well as the activities of the technical work package WP4 and their engagement with the fair AI that resulted with the creation of the AI Ethical Demonstrator which is presented in D2.4. This playful demonstrator accompanied with the set of assessment questions that explain

ethical considerations distilled from the AI Act, serves primarily as a reflection tool for every tech developer before building any AI tool. **Engagement and Co-Creation:** Deliverables D2.3, D2.4 and D2.7 explore literature sources addressing genuine engagement with communities, concept of marginalisation, notion of intersectionality and framework of design justice that recommends design efforts should start from communities themselves, through the bottom-up initiatives. In this idealised worldview, a designer is seen not as an expert but one of the community members, that organizes the community in relation to issues of technological innovations.

Carrying out tasks in the WP2

The deliverable D2.4 gives an overview of the frameworks and tools that enable the various project activities to engage the target groups and adopt existing solutions to fit their needs in an ethical and inclusive manner (contributing to D2.1) and tackling the tasks of **T2.3**. A set of questions to provide insight into a community's needs is initially provided in D2.3 and consolidated in D2.4, referring to tasks i) of **T2.3**. Furthermore, the checklists with questions for city administrations to enable ethical and inclusive piloting with marginalised communities is provided in D2.6.

Based on the learnings from the piloting, the recorded needs of marginalised communities are translated through design methods into a visualisation that provides the professionals who adapt existing solutions a rich understanding of the needs. These visualisations are part of D2.2, D2.7 and D2.9 and consolidated in D6.1. Furthermore, the checklists with questions for city administrations to enable ethical and inclusive piloting with marginalised communities provided in D2.6, are visualised and incorporated to the CommuniLab, addressing task ii) of **T2.3**.

Lists of requirements for the technical adaptations of an existing solution in ethical and inclusive manner are incorporated in various deliverables of WP2: D2.3 and D2.4 contain lists of questions for tech developers when engaging with marginalised communities; D2.8 and D2.9 sets the ethical requirements and principles for co-creation; D2.6 provides checklists for cities involved in innovation with marginalised communities. Furthermore, deliverable D2.4 includes the technical solution built by partners from WP4- The Pedagogic Demonstrator, a reflective tool for pilot teams to familiarize with the features of European AI Act. The knowledge and learnings contained in the mentioned WP2 deliverables, collectively compiled in the CommuniLab, represents a comprehensive set

of requirements for stakeholders leading the piloting process with marginalised communities, being either tech developers or city administrations conducting these processes.

In this document we have included a remark to stakeholders' meetings that have been organised by various cities. The example of these meetings organized in the two piloting rounds (first and third) is from Amsterdam is a format of "Stakeholder dinner" presented in the Box 2, contributing to task T2.4: local intermediaries, users, technology providers and civil servants were brought together in order to analyse bottlenecks.

All WP2 deliverables addresses various project tasks: outline methods for effectively adapting technological tools for marginalised communities, with a focus on reflection (D2.9, D2.3, D2.7), empathy and co-creation (D2.2), direct engagement, and community organising (D2.3 and D2.7). They emphasize embedding reflection into the innovation process by design (D2.4) and integrating ethics and inclusion into the infrastructure from the outset (D2.6), addressing in this way task i) from the **T2.5**.

All mentioned deliverables offer different visualization options using various methods—graphic design and translating into tangible reflection tools like A Co-Creation Reboot CardSet (D2.9), hand-drawn cards in a comic format (D2.7), or slideshows with checklists for ethical piloting (D2.6). Learning reflections from WP2 were integrated into key guiding documents for piloting—the Open Call Manual and the Piloting Manual developed by WP3 and WP5. Monitoring of uptakes was ensured through regular stakeholder meetings during the piloting process and data collection embedded into the piloting by-design. In this way task ii), iii) and iv) from **T2.5** are addressed.

Learnings about co-creation in CommuniCity

A foundation for the guidelines expressed in this deliverable comes from the knowledge and learnings about co-creation developed throughout the CommuniCity project. In this chapter, we will provide:

- a brief overview of the **knowledge artefacts** produced by all partners in WP2 (deliverables, co-creation tools, models, principles, frameworks);
- a **survey analysis**: analysis of opinions and attitudes of tech-developers, as expressed in the surveys that are part of the mandatory final piloting reports;
- an elaboration on ethnographic **observations** conducted during meetings of the project beneficiaries in charge of the implementation of the piloting model (in WP3 and WP5), as well as through on the ground observations in selected pilot meetings.
- **case studies** with good practices of co-creation observed in the project.

Based on established knowledge, we formulate 7 key guidelines for future endeavours in urban tech innovations with marginalised communities

2.1 Knowledge produced by WP2 partners

The CommuniCity project consists of 7 Work Packages. Following the original project proposal, the role of WP2 was to reflect on the co-learning activities set up across the various stakeholders involved in the project and pilots. Project-wise, it was the place where results of all other WPs converged, in turn providing guidance to support the project objectives. As shown in Figure 1, the critical reflection and learning loops were embedded in the CommuniCity project by-design, with accompanying roles and tasks assigned to the partners in the WP2.

Independently from the guidance process, observations have been important to WP2's activities. Qualitative mixed methods were used throughout the project. Data was collected through surveys, interviews, participatory observation, project documents' analysis, and literature review, in order to produce the project deliverables associated with WP2 as well as scientific publications. The data was gathered individually by all research partners involved in WP2 through personalized approaches and arrangements

with participants in the piloting process (city administrations, civil society organizations, tech developers). Additionally, the piloting process from the WP5 itself included a built-in, by-design, data collection process from tech developers who led the selected pilots, using mandatory questionnaires during mid-term and final reporting. Furthermore, a WP2 representative was involved in meeting ethnography through participative observation of the regular meetings of WP3/5 piloting beneficiaries, as well as pilot meetings in selected cities.

Figure 1. Feedback loops between work packages in the CommuniCity project (from DoA)

All research partners in WP2 – Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), Demos Helsinki (DH), and University of Amsterdam (UA), together with partners from practice – Municipality Amsterdam (AMS) and ENoLL – produced deliverables and knowledge on various aspects of the piloting process in CommuniCity, with a focus on co-creation. This knowledge has been embedded in all WP2 deliverables (from D2.1 to D2.9) and covers various approaches, from practical to reflective and speculative and abstract. In the

following we provide a selected view of the main results and learnings relevant for co-creation.

2.1.1 Co-creation tools

Co-creation Methods Toolbox

In addition to actively leading and participating in the piloting processes, the City of Amsterdam (AMS) contributed to the project's research in their deliverable D2.2. The experiences gained in the pilots and the research conducted by interviewing (experienced) experts, organising or participating in meetings and workshops have led to the development of the process for incremental improvement and matching needs of local citizens and communities to solutions offered by technology providers. Insights gained from these activities contextualised the position of marginalised groups and their challenges, the role of technology as a contributor to solving societal challenges, and identifies the main bottlenecks in the process of creating impact and co-creation. The resulting process, along with the accompanying practical toolkit offering actionable guidance, constitutes the principal contributions of this work. Findings related to a set of methods and tips suitable for co-creation with marginalised communities has been visualised and integrated to the knowledge repository CommuniLab (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Categories of co-creation methods developed by the Municipality of Amsterdam (AMS) within a toolbox² (from D2.2).

² <https://communicity-project.eu/interface-toolbox-communicity-co-creation-with-marginalised-groups>

The deliverable D2.2 provides a comprehensive overview of various research and co-creation techniques and methods that can be selected for each phase of an innovation project, in particular to phases 1 to 4, as described in the following:

Phase 1: Detecting challenges. Suggested research methods that help identify pressing social challenges and specific issues faced by target groups, providing insights for problem definition are *Research into current issues* and *Focus on a specific target group*, while suggested Co-creation methods that in this phase actively involve the community or target groups to deepen understanding and foster empowerment are as following: *Guided tour, Peers observing Peers, Photojournal and Card Sort*.

Phase 2: Articulating the needs. To thoroughly understand a challenge, it's essential to refine it, empathize with the target audience, and determine the desired impact, using research methods to scope challenges and co-creation methods to engage and understand the target group. Suggested research methods are *Frame your design challenge, Align on your impact goals, Define your audience, Design Project Scoping Guide, Articulating the challenge*, while co-creation methods are listed as following: *Bodystorming, Empathy timeline, Collage and Problem framing*.

Phase 3. Matching tech partners. Developing tech solutions for social problems is still uncommon due to resource constraints, so clear challenges and thorough preparation are essential. Research methods suggested in this phase are as follows: *Involving Social Designers, Open Call, Hackathon and Matching Platform*, while proposed co-creation methods are: *Matching meeting and Composition of the jury*.

Phase 4: Developing tech solutions. When developing tech for marginalised groups, co-creation—especially through the five phases of Design Thinking: *Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test*—is essential to ensure solutions meet their real needs and achieve high adoption. For every phase, a variety of research and co-creation methods are proposed.

A set of co-creation methods and tips has been presented in the second and third round to piloting teams, and demonstrated during consortium meetings in Amsterdam (June 2024), EnoLL event - the 2024 edition of OpenLivingLab Days held in Timișoara, Romania (September 2024) and final event in Porto (July 2025).

Co-creation Reboot Card Set

Based on the final *Principles of ethical and inclusive engagement* and research insights that will be described in the next section, the Amsterdam University of Applied Science (AUAS) developed the Co-creation Reboot Card Set shown in Figure 3. This tool incorporates reflective questions into the co-creation process to help pilots adapt their processes to better address the needs of the community. Reflexive practices in design are recognized for fostering critical awareness and deeper engagement with complex social issues. Reflection enables practitioners to challenge assumptions, embrace diverse perspectives, and iteratively refine their work. The card set's goal is to support pilot teams to identify blind spots, realign practices, and ensure that their approach remains responsive to the evolving needs of the communities they work with. By integrating these questions, pilot teams can engage in a continuous, iterative, and reflective process at every stage.

Figure 3. The Co-creation Reboot Card Set developed by AUAS (from D2.8 and D2.9).

The cards are connected to the principles outlined in Figure 4. For instance, for the first principle "**Champion Inclusivity**", six cards in the deck offer propositions for reflection such as:

- **Question.** Everyone brings something unique in a co-creation process. Which talent or super-power do you enjoy using?
- **Dilemma.** Sometimes it takes effort and a lot of time to help newcomers connect in the process. What is your position?
 - The reality is that there is too little time for this.

- I invest time in engaging the newcomers.
- **Question.** *Co-creation often means giving up something for the greater good. What is your experience in this? Are there things that are non-negotiable for you?*
- **Statement.** *If we can't get hold of certain people, or can't talk to them, we work with assumptions about them. Sometimes that's just the way it is. (Agree—Disagree)*
- **Dilemma.** *In complex decisions, the final decision is often made by the person with the most responsibility. (This is inevitable. -- I'm not okay with this.)*
- **Question.** *Can you give some examples- small or big- of how you try and make a co-creation process more inclusive?*

The Co-Creation Reboot Card Set³ developed by AUAS highlights the importance of introducing reflective moments in the piloting process and offers a comprehensive list of propositions that can inspire discussion and reflection during co-creation. The card Set was distributed to the piloting teams during the third round of pilots, and its practical effect tested during the final project event in Porto.

2.1.2 Principles, Frameworks, and Models

Principles of ethical and inclusive engagement

In deliverables D2.8 and D2.9, the Amsterdam University of Applied Science (AUAS) developed a set of principles of ethical and inclusive engagement based on research from the first two rounds of CommuniCity pilots. They are as following:

1. **Champion Inclusivity:** Ensure equal and meaningful participation by engaging communities early and removing barriers to participation.
2. **Strengthen Connections:** Build trust through transparent communication, active listening, and acknowledging cultural, language, and geographical differences.
3. **Coordinate with Empathy:** Address challenges proactively by clarifying roles and providing flexibility in timelines and budgets for community participation.
4. **Open Up to Context:** Adapt co-creation efforts to the community's unique needs and foster lasting support networks for long-term resilience.

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15902161>

5. **Frame the Bigger Picture:** Guide co-creation with a clear vision focused on social, ethical, and cultural goals, emphasizing long-term sustainability.

AUAS reorganised these principles visually, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Principles of ethical and inclusive engagement, developed by AUAS (D2.9)

AUAS research suggests that future smart city initiatives where co-creation plays a central role can benefit greatly from ongoing reflection throughout the process. Regular moments of reflection can help identify blind spots, adjust collaboration strategies, and ensure that all voices remain genuinely included.

Ethics and Inclusivity Framework

After the initial version based on literature reviews and analysis of other similar frameworks (D2.5), Demos Helsinki (DH) has created an updated version of *Ethics and Inclusivity Framework* in D2.6, a normative framework for cities interested in tech-focused piloting for urban innovation. The framework is grounded in empirical insights derived from qualitative research through ethnographic observation of the pilots in the first and second piloting rounds (the original first round cities of Helsinki and Amsterdam and their experiences were complemented with insights from Aarhus, Breda and Prague), data

analysis from midterm and final reports, interviews, and other methods. The framework is recommended for cities interested in tech-focused piloting for urban innovations in order to assess (i) if the CommuniCity approach suits the city wishing to start piloting processes, and (ii) if the city is able to implement it in an ethical manner. The framework guides cities throughout the five phases of the innovation process, visualized in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Phases of the innovation process with marginalised communities as defined in the Ethics and Inclusivity Framework by Demos Helsinki (from D2.6)

The Ethics and Intersectional Inclusivity Framework blends social and technical dimensions to support ethical practices in open calls and pilots, and draws on benchmarks of existing models and a broad range of theoretical discussions.

The Framework highlights the importance of recognising power dynamics, favouring co-creation with people whose lives the pilots touch upon, considering non-technological solutions and maintaining inclusive practices. It also recommends establishing mechanisms for anticipating and mitigating unintended consequences, thus ensuring that pilots promote equity, accountability, and long-term community trust.

First and foremost, the Framework speaks to cities as they are recognised as key accountability holders in the CommuniCity approach. The Framework supports city actors to explore whether they can act as accountable managers and hosts in a setting

that involves vulnerable and marginalised groups. It serves both as a diagnostic and guiding tool to engage in ethically-grounded, inclusive technology piloting. It acknowledges the tension between innovation and accountability: while cities may share in the success of high-profile pilots, they must also be prepared to take responsibility for shortcomings or ethical oversight.

The Framework encompasses a background report (Deliverable 2.6) and a slide deck which is included as a resource in the CommuniLab⁴ and thus made more easily available for the broader public.

The Framework walks cities through five iterative phases: setting up, before, during, after, and post-pilot follow-through. For each there is a **Preparation Guide** and a **Checklist** that helps to concretize the guidance. The key questions include the following:

Setting Up: Is this approach something for your city?

Before Piloting: Can you do the required footwork to encourage co-creation by the vulnerable?

During Piloting: Do you find the balance of being a generous facilitator and a firm guardian of the key principles?

After Piloting: Is your city ready to sometimes share the fame but always take the eventual blame?

Post-pilot follow-through: Has your city documented the learnings and do they lead forward?

Finally, the Framework also offers advice for the design of research and innovation funding schemes that may contain piloting with vulnerable groups.

Critical questions from Design Justice

After reviewing the knowledge and methodologies acquired in the previous OrganiCity and SynchroniCity projects and recognizing the unique focus of the CommuniCity project (co-creation with marginalised communities), the University of Amsterdam (UA) engaged in D2.3 with a critical analysis and evaluation, drawing from scholarly literature, of the concept of co-creation across all relevant dimensions in the given context. While OrganiCity and SynchroniCity effectively highlighted co-creation in their projects and

⁴ <https://communicity-project.eu/ethical-framework/>

generated associated documents, they in practice applied a top-down-oriented approach to innovation, led mostly by tech parties in the context of a market-driven rationale, with target groups very different from marginalised communities. A design justice approach to socio-technical interventions, in contrast, emphasises the importance of community-led practices to empower marginalised communities to re-imagine cities that they need. Also, some of the partners within the WP2 like AUAS and DH utilized elements of the design justice perspective in their deliverables, aiming to look at the practical pilots in CommuniCity. In the deliverable D2.3 an outline of an evaluative framework informed by a design-justice perspective on **“co-creation for-with-by”** was developed, which is further operationalised in presentations among consortia partners. In the same deliverable D2.3, UA has developed a set of critical questions that could support conducting more inclusive co-creation activities with marginalised groups based on design justice principles, here reported in the Table 1.

Combining the ten principles of Design justice (DJ)⁵ with three axes (why, who, and how), UA proposed a preliminary list of evaluative questions (Table 2), which could support conducting more inclusive co-creation activities with marginalised groups.

	DJ Principle	Questions
WHY (our purpose, our vision and our values embedded in the pilot or co-creation activity)	1	Does the pilot have a social and equitable mission? Is it intended to improve social outcomes and correct systemic inequities?
	8	Does the pilot include a commitment to accountability to the communities? Is it designed by community members and does it include a sustainability component?
	9	Does the pilot have an environmental component to not only mitigate adverse impacts but nurture positive outcomes? Does the pilot include a social, human rights, gender, or environmental impact assessment?
	10	Does the pilot include recognition of past work on the topic with an emphasis on locally generated, indigenous knowledge, and practice? Does the pilot include a literature review, systematic review, interviews with local knowledge bearers, etc.?

⁵ Design Justice Network Principles: <https://designjustice.org/read-the-principles>

<p>WHO</p> <p>(our actors, allies, and advocates embedded in our pilot or co-creation activity)</p>	5	<p>Who is conducting the pilot and how do they impact the work? What are the roles and responsibilities of the designer or other piloting team members?</p> <p>Is the pilot co-designed or co-implemented with the community in question? Are we adequately listening to and capturing all perspectives from the studied community?</p> <p>Does the pilot lead approach the design process, not as an expert, but as a facilitator who does not have the full knowledge of the community in question?</p> <p>Does the pilot recognize the blind spots of the designer?</p>
	6	<p>Does the design place value on the contributions of the team participants or communities as experts of their own experiences? Does the pilot allow for co-design, adaptation, or any way for participants to contribute to the research process?</p>
<p>HOW</p> <p>How are we conducting the pilot and co-creation activity? Reflecting on the process, and its impact can bring some realizations to steps along the way that can centre the communities and participant voices who are considered the subject. This is a key element of ensuring the design process is just and equitable.</p>	2	<p>Are we acknowledging that the pilot, both in its process and its findings, can have long-term effects on participants?</p> <p>Is the design centring their voices?</p>
	3	<p>Is the pilot's impact on the community prioritized over the pilot's intentions?</p> <p>Could there be unintended outcomes? What is the meaning of free, prior, and informed consent in this context?</p>
	4	<p>Is there a commitment and series of actions that ensure that a piloting process is transparent, collaborative, and social change-oriented? Is the piloting process evaluated continuously and iterated for increased accessibility, accountability, and collaboration?</p>
	7	<p>Is there a mechanism for training and knowledge sharing with the communities that are being studied?</p> <p>Does the design process include a component in which we report back to the communities and ensure that it is a productive and constructive process for everyone involved?</p>

Table 1. List of critical questions supporting more inclusive co-creation for/with/by marginalised communities (derived from D2.3 produced by UA).

Cloud Weaving Model

The new co-creation methods proposed in deliverables D2.3 (Design Justice approach) and D2.7 (the Cloud Weaving Model) conceptualize the role of the tech designer as a community organizer. Community organising refers to a process in which members of a community come together to take collective action on social issues that impact them

all, often requiring professional facilitation and support⁶. While analysing challenges in pilot projects developing AI with marginalised communities, as well as in elaborating those challenges to the project partners, UA researchers found it difficult to express them within commonly used paradigms (e.g. software-engineering terminology and processes). They therefore constructed in D2.7 an alternative conceptual framework to ground AI development in the social fabric – the *Cloud Weaving Model* – inspired (amongst others) by indigenous knowledge, motifs from nature, and Eastern traditions. D2.7 introduces and elaborates on the fundamental elements of the model (clouds, spiders, threads, spiderwebs, and weather) and their interpretation in an AI context. In general, metaphors present translation challenges due to their linguistic and cultural complexities, leaving the translation process intrinsically open to diverse cultural interpretations. However, people not only talk metaphorically- they also think and feel metaphorically. As metaphors have their basis in bodily interactions with the physical world, they have the potential to alter how we think and feel about various topics.

Figure 6. The Cloud Weaving Model, a reflective, imaginative tool for co-creation with marginalised communities developed by UA (from D2.7).

⁶ Christens, B.D., Speer, P.W.: Community Organizing: Practice, Research, and Policy Implications. *Social Issues and Policy Review* 9(1), 193–222 (2015).

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/sipr.12014>,

<https://spssi.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/sipr.12014>

The metaphor expressed by the Cloud Weaving model (Figure 6) invites practitioners to envision ethical and responsible tech development as a relational process, rather than an endpoint: **tech as a practice, rather than a product**.

The model at this stage serves primarily as an interpretative tool, meant for critical reflection, calling on all participants in tech innovations with marginalised communities to pause and reflect on their role in the process, encouraging them to imagine it otherwise.

2.2 Knowledge produced from surveys' analysis

During the piloting process, each “pilot team” (primarily led by the tech developers implementing the pilot) produced two key documents: a *midterm* and a *final report*⁷, (meant to track progress, share key learnings, and facilitate communication among stakeholders. These final reports have been a primary data source for the CommuniCity project's insights, though “teams should be ready to provide additional content if needed”, as reported in the Piloting Manual⁸. Midterm and final reports are created in the form of questionnaires, where the pilot teams answer the set of questions related to the pilot implementation, the technical framework and stream of co-creation processes. These surveys are part of the document package that is distributed to the selected pilot teams. Data collected from tech developers are available for internal usage by project partners. Research partners from WP2 were approached on several occasions by partners running the open calls and piloting processes with the question to analyse the collected data.

2.2.1 What pilot questionnaires says about co-creation

The process of co-creation was represented in the midterm and final reports of all pilot teams in the three piloting rounds, through the questions expressed in Table 2. Number and content of questions related to co-creation has evolved incrementally throughout the three piloting rounds, aiming to capture co-creation experience from the point of view of tech-developers.

⁷ According to one of the partners leading the open calls and piloting process, in the time of writing this report, the total number of these reports were approximately 170.

⁸ <https://manuals.communicity-project.eu/piloting/>

Piloting round	Questions about co-creation	
	Midterm report	Final report
Round 1	<p>No explicit question about co-creation</p> <p>Another question that yielded information on challenges reaching marginalised communities:</p> <p>- <i>What have you learned from piloting so far?</i></p>	<p>1. <i>Describe all the co-creation methods and co-learning activities applied.</i></p> <p>2. <i>How did you ensure that the target group members' had a positive piloting experience?</i></p> <p>3. <i>Write a short publishable summary of your pilot, including objectives, description of the piloting process and co-creation activities, the results and the next steps.</i></p> <p>Additional question that yielded information on challenges in co-creation with marginalised communities:</p> <p>- <i>What have you learned during the piloting?</i></p>

<p>Round 2</p>	<p>1. What co-creation activities have you already carried out? Please list and describe the method, target group(s) and number of participants.</p> <p>2. How do you find the co-creation activities impacting your pilot so far? Please share (if any) examples or issues.</p> <p>3. Tips or suggestions, big or small, to share with future pilot teams regarding the co-creation and collaboration?</p> <p>Other questions that yielded information on challenges in co-creation with marginalised communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What were the biggest challenges in the application process related to the writing of the proposal, planning the pilot, establishing the piloting team and submitting the application? - What have you learned from the piloting so far? - What kind of challenges (if any) have you experienced during the piloting? Please elaborate the challenges and how you overcame them, or state if the situation is still to be solved. 	<p>1. What does the term "co-creation" mean to you?</p> <p>2. Describe all co-creation activities organised in terms of method, frequency, duration and location. Provide a minimum detailed description per event. For instance: Event 1: Workshop on outdoor exercising with 2 nurses and 5 clients from the Home Care department at a local Day Active Centre. Event 2: ...</p> <p>3. What aspects of co-creation in your pilot would you like to highlight as successful?</p> <p>4. Could you describe any challenges or barriers encountered with co-creation during your pilot? Please elaborate the challenge/barrier and possible solution.</p> <p>5. Which were the main obstacles in organising co-creation activities with the target group (select the most important ones): identifying and involving the community; communication issues; knowledge gap; language gap; other.</p> <p>6. If you answered 'other', please elaborate what obstacles were detected.</p> <p>7. How many co-creation events were organised in your pilot?</p> <p>8. How many organisations, or departments of the city, in total participated in these events?</p> <p>9. How many individual participants in total participated in these events?</p> <p>10. How many of the participants represented the target group of the pilot?</p> <p>11. Did you succeed in involving the target group in the co-creation process? Please elaborate.</p> <p>12. In what way does the end product reflect the needs of the target group members?</p> <p>13. How did you ensure that the target group members had a positive piloting experience?</p> <p>14. Which series of actions do you think ensured that the co-creation process was transparent, collaborative, and social change-oriented?</p> <p>15. What knowledge about the marginalised group have you had before running the pilot? Which were the sources for this knowledge? What knowledge about the marginalised group have you gained</p>
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		<p><i>from this pilot?</i></p> <p>16. <i>Which (type of) input from the marginalised group you think was the most important during the co-creation process?</i></p> <p>17. <i>Do you plan follow-up activities with the target group? If yes, which ones?</i></p> <p>18. <i>Could you offer tips or suggestions, big or small, to share with future pilot teams regarding co-creation and collaboration?</i></p> <p>19. <i>Write a short publishable summary of your pilot, including objectives, description of the piloting process and co-creation activities, the results and the next steps. Write it to the reader who has not heard of the pilot before but who is familiar with the CommuniCity project. Avoid commercial content and avoid using first person pronouns, please.</i></p> <p>Other questions that yielded information on challenges in co-creation marginalised communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>How did the target group perceive co-creation and the technical solution?</i> - <i>What did you learn from co-creating with the target group?</i>
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<p>Round 3</p>	<p>1. Describe the co-creation activities you have already carried out, including the methods, locations and participants (number of people, type of stakeholder), and number of sessions.</p> <p>2. Have you encountered any barriers with co-creation during your pilot so far? If so, please describe the barrier(s) and how you addressed it.</p> <p>3. How are you ensuring that the pilot is a positive experience for the participants from marginalised communities?</p> <p>4. How have the co-creation activities influenced your pilot so far? Please share any positive examples or challenges you've encountered.</p> <p>5. Tips or suggestions, big or small, to share with future pilot teams regarding the co-creation and collaboration?</p> <p>Another question that yielded information on challenges in co-creation with marginalised communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What were the biggest challenges in the application process related to the writing of the proposal, planning the pilot, establishing the piloting team and submitting the application? 	<p>1. Describe the co-creation activities during the pilot, including the methods, locations, participants and number of sessions.</p> <p>2. Estimation of the number of people participating in your co-creation activities.</p> <p>3. How many of them can be identified as representative of the marginalised group(s) in question? Provide an approximate number of people.</p> <p>4. Which actions, methods or approaches of co-creation you found the most valuable?</p> <p>5. Did you encounter any barriers with co-creation during your pilot? If so, please describe the barrier(s) and how you addressed it.</p> <p>6. How did you ensure that the pilot is a positive experience for the participants from marginalised communities?</p> <p>7. How did you create/maintain a culture of ethical awareness while collaborating with marginalised communities on this pilot? Please describe.</p> <p>8. To what extent did co-creation sessions help create an end product that reflects the needs of the target group members?</p> <p>9. Did you utilise co-creation material provided in CommuniLab (toolbox, webinars, tips & tricks, etc), and if so, how useful did you find it?</p> <p>Other questions that yielded information on challenges in co-creation marginalised communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What has happened since the beginning of the pilot? Describe all the most relevant activities conducted during the entire piloting phase, including any possible deviations between the pilot plan and the actual implementation. - Describe any challenges encountered during the pilot, including how they were addressed or if they remain unresolved.
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Table 2. Co-creation in the questionnaires of the midterms and final reports during three rounds of piloting (source: internal documentation of the CommuniCity project)

2.2.2 Qualitative and Quantitative insights

First round

Users as testers. When asked to describe the activities taken place during the entire piloting phase, including possible deviations, a tech developer running a pilot in Helsinki responded: *“Collecting conversation data. Processing of data. Translation of data. Training a base language model. Build a pilot demo app. Do a user test with real users. Present presentations and provide updates to stakeholders.”* Another tech developer running a pilot in Amsterdam answered the same question: *“Ideation, testing, designing, testing, developing, testing”*. Another tech developer running a pilot in Helsinki said: *“Design sprint (collaboratively designing and planning the solution); Solution development on [...]; Employee training, and instruction documentation for map updating and upkeep; End user testing; meetings”*. Another tech-developer running a pilot in Porto concluded: *“As planned, a pilot took place with a small field test of the system development with the end users”*. From another tech developer running a pilot in Porto we learn that they organised *“user testing sessions: Conducted testing sessions with teachers and students. Gathered feedback to identify areas for improvement”*. Out of 15 responses, most of the surveyed tech-developers described their co-creation sessions as primarily tech-tool testing, which is not unusual in the tech innovation context.

Learnings. For some tech developers even short interaction with the members of their target groups brought important learnings. One tech-developer running a pilot in Amsterdam stated: *“We learned that status holders (refugees) often speak various types of Syrian Arabic, and that it is distinct from classical, Moroccan, Egyptian and other forms of Arabic”*.

Community? Many tech-developers refer to the participants in their co-creation processes as customers, clients or end-users, and see the target group as a marketing segment. Yet, already in this dataset, the topic of “empathy” emerged as important to understand the circumstances and the needs of marginalised communities.

Importance of communication for positive experience during co-creation. Respondents refer to communicating well to understand the needs of the users, being nice and talking with them, empathy – putting yourself in their shoes, collaborative approach, receiving and responding to feedback and being grateful for their efforts. This

confirms benefits of these types of co-creation for changing the attitudes and perceptions of tech developers towards marginalised and vulnerable groups. However, we don't have the opportunity to understand the impact of co-creation activities on participants from marginalised communities. This represents an opportunity for improvement of the CommuniCity piloting process and methodology through introduction of systematic collection of data from marginalised communities.

Quantitative insights. From the type of questions in the survey of the first round, we could extract the frequency of types of interactions occurring during the pilot (Figure 7). Unfortunately, in the survey questions there was little/no information with respect to the specific interaction occurring with the marginalised group. Without this framing, co-creation-related interactions may refer to interactions with intermediaries who are setting up “co-creation” as testing with end users. For instance, representatives of the municipality may arrange meetings for tech developers in elderly care facilities, where tech-developers would go and then test their app.

Figure 7. Frequency of types of interactions occurring in 15 pilots of the first round, as declared in the survey. Note that we could not derive from the collected texts whether/to what extent marginalised groups were involved.

Second round

In the final report of Round 2, tech developers had more space to express their opinion and share insights from the co-creation with marginalised groups in their pilots. Namely, the number of questions related to co-creation significantly increased, from 4 in round 1 to more than 20 in round 2, as shown in Table 2. These questions were suggested by WP2 researchers to the WP5 piloting partners. Despite the extension of the time needed to fill in the report, more open questions such as “What does the term “co-creation” mean to

you?”, resulted in answers with more descriptive quality. The concept of empathy emerged prominently.

Tech-developers acknowledge challenges when working with marginalised communities, admitting low knowledge about marginalised communities before piloting. However, research and co-creation processes of CommuniCity enabled tech developers to gain substantial knowledge about marginalization. According to some CommuniCity partners, this is one of the most significant outcomes of CommuniCity, and should be highlighted. Overall, it could be said that the outcomes of CommuniCity are more directly observed in tech companies and cities' innovation departments, while marginalised communities experience more indirect outcomes mainly derived from tech developers and civil servants becoming more aware of how technology can help solving their problems.

Illustrative is a list of key learnings from one of the tech developers from Round 2 of CommuniCity presented in Box 1.

Box 1. A tech developer on learnings from Round 2 piloting in CommuniCity.

Before running the pilot, our knowledge about the marginalised group was limited. We conducted multiple interviews with representatives from the municipality, coaches, and communities to gain a better understanding. These interviews served as primary sources of knowledge, helping us grasp various aspects of the marginalised group's experiences and challenges. From these interviews, we learned several key insights:

Limited Trust in Government: Some members of the marginalised group expressed scepticism or limited trust in government initiatives, possibly due to past experiences or perceptions.

Feeling Overwhelmed by Projects: The marginalised group felt overwhelmed by the multitude of projects designed for them, suggesting a need for more targeted and streamlined approaches to engagement.

Gender and Family Dynamics: Gender and family dynamics in the area played a significant role in shaping attitudes and behaviours, particularly regarding youngsters' participation in sports activities (families with one parent)

Importance of Parental Involvement: Parents emerged as critical stakeholders in facilitating youngsters participation, highlighting the need to involve and inform them about the app and its objectives.

Ownership and Empowerment: Youngsters expressed a desire to feel ownership of the process and what they create, emphasizing the importance of empowering them to take an active role in shaping their sports experiences.

Learnings expressed by a tech developer in Box 1 could serve as valuable information for the initiators of the innovation processes to inform them about relevant features of marginalised communities. Some of them don't want to relate to the city governments' activities, and this challenge should be addressed with the different, community-led methods of innovation.

Other tech developers in Round 2 acknowledged that *"not everyone needs our solution, but we are focusing on the right target group"*. This insight is important to invite us to reflect on the approach in which tools in high *technology readiness level* (TRL) are brought to the marginalised communities and how that affects their involvement in the co-creation activities. Figure 8 shows the TRL level declared by pilot teams for their product, throughout three rounds of piloting in CommuniCity.

Figure 8. Perceived TRL of pilots in three rounds of CommuniCity (source: final reports of pilots, n= 90)

In Round 2, some tech developers realised the possibility to go beyond tool-driven approach and engage for the wider benefits of the community. One of the pilots took a capacity-building approach and trained four youth workers to become specialists in specific technology hoping that *"they will maintain this role and act as the driving force behind this development within their teams. In a year, they will have trained several colleagues in this methodology"*. Another pilot went beyond mere digital tech-development focus and included physical activities for participants from involved marginalised communities. One pilot team changed its original idea and offered literacy

training to members of marginalised groups. Figure 9 shows frequency of interactions in the second CommuniCity piloting round.

Figure 9. Frequency of types of interactions occurring in 16 pilots of the second round, as declared in the survey. Note that we could not derive from the collected texts whether/to what extent marginalised groups were involved.

Reports from round 2 offer several accounts where flexibility and awareness were demonstrated. For instance, when faced with unsolvable problems, tech developers would make bold decisions and either profoundly alter the original plan, or choose to offer an analogue tool instead of a digital one as a response to the needs of the marginalised community. This illustrates the necessity for flexibility with the tech-driven approach in accordance with the signals from the social practice. Tech-developers offer in their final reports valuable lessons on the character of innovation processes as socio-technical and not primarily technical processes. Stories of tech-developers and their reflective insights from the interaction with marginalised communities should be publicly shared in projects like CommuniCity to illustrate complexities and multilayer facets of technological innovations, but also their human character.

Third round

Third round of piloting in CommuniCity extended its innovation approach to larger number of pilots comparing to previous two rounds. Final reports of the Round 3 collected

by the end of June 2025 embedded answers from the pilot teams of 59 pilots. Data analysed in these reports shows the frequency of types of interactions occurring in 59 pilots as shown in the Figure 10. In depth analysis of the selected pilot cases from the round 3 will follow in the next section.

Figure 10. Frequency of types of interactions occurring in 59 pilots of the third round, as declared in the survey. Note that we could not derive from the collected texts whether/to what extent marginalised groups were involved.

Conclusion of the analysis

In this section, we have analysed data collected by piloting teams in CommuniCity in the surveys conducted by piloting partners by design. We have focused on the final reports, as they contain consolidated information about the implemented piloting process, and analysed co-creation represented in these surveys in total of 90 pilots.

General conclusions of this analysis are as following:

- All pilot teams conducted co-creation in their respective pilots and co-creation methods varied- from testing, interviews, surveys, persona creation, to focus groups, etc.
- Tech developers encountered several challenges when aiming to reach members of marginalised communities.

- Some tech developers explain these challenges as limitations imposed by time and budget constraints (each pilot was constrained to 6 months for implementation and a fixed budget of 12.5k EUR).
- In some cases, tech developers arranged co-creation sessions individually, and in other cases in collaboration with public and civic partners which then tried to involve individual members of a certain marginalised group.⁹
- Co-creation sessions yielded important knowledge about marginalised communities that resulted in the improvement of the design in meeting the needs of a given group, and in some cases with the empathy for living conditions of the marginalised communities.
- Co-creation was mainly meant to support pilot design efforts serving needs of individual users or a particular organisation.
- lack of skills, resources and specific budget for co-creation activities on behalf of tech-developers and other stakeholders limited scope of co-creation.

Furthermore, the predominant form of co-creation was testing with 52 pilots using this method. Yet, some co-creation activities during pilots have had also an added value with capacity building activities, trainings and consultations that tech-developers conducted with various stakeholders, mostly public services as indicated in Helsinki or civil society organisations as reported in Porto or Amsterdam.

When analysing types of co-creation based on the focus of the pilot (product, service or community building), leading role in co-creation, decision making and ownership of the final technical solution created during pilot, four distinct approaches to co-creation can be distinguished:

- **Co-creation “for”** has in focus product or service creation or improvement, is led by tech-developer in limited collaboration with public or civic partner with the main aim to test the tool. Decisions about co-creation have been made by the tech-developer who also retains the ownership over the tool.
- **Co-creation “for/with”** has similar characteristics as previous approach to co-creation, with the significant difference that the decisions regarding co-creation activities have been made in closer collaboration between tech-developers and public or civic partners. Co-creation for/with also opens the possibility for future partnerships among these stakeholders related to the sustainability of the tool and potential shared ownership.

⁹ In Porto, for example – the initial contact was primarily made with civil society organisations, which then (and not always) involved individual members of a certain marginalised group.

- **Co-creation “with”** highlights the strong collaboration of tech-developers with public or civic stakeholders and equal roles in co-creation processes.
- **Co-creation “by”** underlines the leading role of the communities in the co-creation both in challenges formulation and throughout piloting process, assuming the decision making and ownership of the tool stay by the community.

The four types of co-creation defined above identified in the analysis of 90 pilots in three rounds of CommuniCity are represented in the Figure 11.

Figure 11. Cumulative co-creation methods in three rounds of CommuniCity

Figure 11 shows that the predominant forms of co-creation in the CommuniCity project were co-creation *for* and co-creation *for/with*. Distribution of co-creation methods varied by the cities, with some of the co-creation methods more present in some cities, than others, as shown in the Figure 12.

Figure 12. Cumulative co-creation methods per city in CommuniCity three rounds of piloting (n=90 pilots)

Among leading partnering cities, Porto has employed specific approach during piloting rounds of CommuniCity which we describe in more details in Box 2:

Box 2. Porto Approach to piloting and co-creation in CommuniCity.

Sara Neves from Domus Social explains peculiarity of Porto approach to piloting and co-creation during CommuniCity:

General target audience defined. An important aspect of the CommuniCity implementation in Porto, which I believe was not replicated in other cities, is that we defined a general target audience to which all the challenges in Porto, across all rounds, were addressed. In my opinion, this is a key point because it allowed CommuniCity to have a presence on the ground for two years, rather than just six months. Even though the people who participated directly in each pilot varied from one pilot to another.

Narrowing down the pilot area. Since Domus Social manages the municipal housing in Porto, we (Porto Digital (PD) and Domus Social (DS)) decided to target open calls to the municipal tenants – which, unlike other countries, are in their majority, people that are at an economic and/or social disadvantaged situation. Domus Social manages around 13.000 housing units, so we decided to narrow down the pilot area. For that purpose, we have selected the territory of “ARU da Corujeira” (ARU means “Area of Urban Rehabilitation”, and it is an urban tool to delimit and prioritize areas that are degraded or lacks basic urban services, putting into question its use, safety of

healthiness, so it is defined as a priority intervention area of integrated urban rehabilitation). Besides these urban issues, this is the city's area with the biggest concentration of social housing (around 40% of the population lives in public housing). It is an area that is, additionally, geographically clearly delimited – it was originally and naturally separated by a valley, but this valley, over time, was densified with urban transport infrastructure and it is now a kind of island, surrounded by the two main road axes of the city, that allow high-speed traffic.

Specifying target groups for each pilot. In this way, we clearly defined our target audience, but it is still quite a broad audience (8 municipal public housing districts, where around 5.800 people live). Therefore, for each challenge/pilot, there was a specific target group (isolated elderly people, children of a certain school year, etc.). The idea behind this strategy was that people, even if not directly involved in a pilot, would become aware of CommuniCity indirectly, because they share a common territory with a highly interconnected internal dynamic, facilitating the understanding of the CommuniCity project (because it complex to grasp – something we also witnessed in the ground) and thus organically spreading the importance and potential of technology applied to solving everyday issues.

2.3 Knowledge from process observation

The innovation model applied in CommuniCity, called the *CommuniCity Agile Piloting Process*¹⁰, is derived from previous projects (amongst others, OrganiCity and SynchroniCity, see their overview given in D2.3) and experiences in the field of digital and social innovation of prominent members of the project consortium. Through these previous projects, partners have accumulated and crafted procedural knowledge and best practices in this respect, becoming recognized references, resulting in the effective delivery of an impressive number of pilots across Europe in relatively little time during the CommuniCity project. The present chapter will therefore focus on reflecting on the CommuniCity project as a process, regarding its aim of improving engagement with marginalised communities. Based on research findings stemming mostly from the meeting ethnography, we will elaborate socio-ethical considerations of this particular innovation model from the perspective of its epistemological scope, rather than organizational, managerial or moral dimensions.

¹⁰ <https://communicity-project.eu/about/>

Figure 13. The CommuniCity Agile Piloting Process as presented in the project documentation

2.3.1 The CommuniCity Agile Piloting Process

The official documentation of the model defines 4 key steps in the process (see Figure 13), yet, with two processes preceding and following them, the process consists of de-facto 6 phases, distributed across different actors.

Step	Activity	Main actor leading the activity (role)
1	Define challenge	Cities/ Public innovation agencies
2	Setup and Run Open Call	Public innovation agency/Cities
3	Select pilots	Cities/ Public innovation agencies
4	Piloting	Pilot teams (mostly tech developers)
5	Wrap-up	Innovation agency/Cities
6	Collect results	Innovation agency/Cities

Table 4. Phases of the CommuniCity Agile Piloting process, with main leading actors

Systematic considerations

Looking at the presented process from a systematic point of view, we can make a number of observations.

Operation-oriented. The sequential nature of the proposed innovation model makes its operational nature manifest. Yet, to fulfil the research objectives of WP2, the CommuniCity project had an additional activity of critical *observation and reflection* which has been conducted longitudinally across all phases, with researchers of UA participating as observers in regular weekly meetings amongst piloting partners from WP3 and WP5 during second and third round of piloting, as well as during pilots' meetings mostly in Amsterdam. This additional activity provided crucial opportunities of reflection, learning and adaptation. Complementary, during the first round, UA researchers have participated in the co-creation activities of pilots and a focus group with pilot hosts in Amsterdam. During the second piloting round, UA researchers conducted a survey with pilot managers from partnering cities Helsinki, Amsterdam and Porto, as well as with replicator cities Breda, Tallinn, Prague and Aarhus. UA researchers conducted a focus group with mentioned replicator cities at the end of round two. In the third round, UA researchers conducted a focus group with pilot hosts, and participated in the pilot meetings (kick-off, midterm or final meeting) of eight pilots in Amsterdam. Furthermore, UA researchers participated at the kick off meeting of 6 pilots in Sarajevo. Finally, interviews with pilots from Manchester, Amsterdam and Porto have been conducted for the purpose of this deliverable. Owing to budgetary constraints, as well as overlapping commitments and the expedited nature of the pilot process, most UA research activities during the pilot phase were carried out in Amsterdam. For detailed information about research methodologies and collection of data by other WP2 partners (AUAS and DH), please consult their respective deliverables finalized in the second reporting period- D2.6 and D2.9.

Centralized governance. The first three actions of the model (defining challenge, setting up and running open call, and selecting pilots) are led primarily by the public stakeholders- cities or city founded legal bodies (innovation agencies established as non-profits or public companies)¹¹. The fifth action (systematic data collecting through

¹¹ For example, In Porto, the city was not directly involved in the CommuniCity process (except in one or two specific challenges, in the role of Pilot Host). All mentioned phases were led by the innovation "agency" (Porto Digital) with the support of the social housing "agency" (Domus Social).

midterm and final reports embedded in the process design) was led by the innovation agency. This rather centralized model, which ensures effectiveness and streamlining, may hinder openness to needs which are not acknowledged yet at central level.

Data collection strategies. For the centralization realised by step 6, the model enables systematic communication with the leaders of pilot teams. (During the three rounds, they were predominantly tech developers, except in several cases.) Communication is planned to occur *by-design* after the selected pilots are chosen and contracts are signed. During the piloting process, tech developers participate in mandatory meetings and complete surveys called *Midterm* and *Final reports*. The data in these questionnaires serve as the primary source of information about the pilots, including co-creation from the perspective of the tech developers. We provide an analysis of this collected data in section 1.2. Similar systematic efforts do not exist for capturing opinions and attitudes of marginalised communities, nor public servants involved in the process, nor general public or media within the involved communities.

However, during the CommuniCity implementation, various *ad-hoc* initiatives to capture opinions of various stakeholders in the piloting process¹² (among them also marginalised communities) were invented. One of them, realised in Amsterdam, is described in section Box 3.

Box 3. *Stakeholders' dinners in Amsterdam*

Although not systematically integrated into the reporting system of the CommuniCity project, the opportunity for civil society representatives and marginalised groups to voice their opinions was facilitated through individual initiatives by the leading cities. For example, in Amsterdam, during the first and the third round of piloting, a joint working dinner was organised, involving representatives from all stakeholders engaged in the piloting process. Stakeholders were divided into groups, and after dinner, they held reflection discussions on topics related to the piloting. These conversations were structured and led by a moderator, with notes taken afterward. One of the authors of this report attended all these working dinners in Amsterdam, participating in the pilot hosts group, which included representatives from public services providing support to marginalised groups and civil society organizations advocating for different marginalised communities.

Notably, there was palpable enthusiasm among this group for participating in tech innovation

¹² Furthermore, in some cases, like Helsinki, the piloting teams had their own questionnaires and data-gathering sessions.

processes and a willingness to thoroughly explain the needs of their users and the challenges they face in daily work, as well as to explore the potential benefits that technological solutions could offer. Simultaneously, discussions also addressed the challenges such solutions might pose. Primarily, concerns were expressed regarding (i) privacy issues, data collection and storage, and the (ii) maintenance of technological solutions. Some commentators posed questions about the fact that (iii) developers from other EU countries were running pilots in Amsterdam, observing that this entailed that “communication is complicated”, and asking “why not somebody local?”. Limitations related to (iv) the duration of pilots and their available resources were also highlighted. Some participants expressed (v) caution about rapid innovation in the social sphere and emphasized the need for more debate with the civil sector. They also touched on topics of (vi) ownership of tech tools and underscored the importance of validating the participation of organizations and their institutional knowledge when publicly communicating or presenting information about developed tech pilots.

2.3.2 Views on Agile piloting

In performing a genealogy of the assumptions underpinning the proposed innovation model, we investigated further the Agile methodology to which it is based upon.

Agile principles

Agile is a term introduced in software development in the 1990s, defining approaches alternative to the Waterfall method (hierarchical, sequential, highly proceduralized). As stated in the famous Agile Manifesto¹³, “On February 11-13, 2001, [...] Representatives from Extreme Programming, SCRUM, DSDM, Adaptive Software Development, Crystal, Feature-Driven Development, Pragmatic Programming, and others sympathetic to the need for an alternative to documentation driven, heavyweight software development processes convened.”

Speed, interaction-centred, result-driven. The most important priority of Agile is to *deliver software*, in a short time, welcoming continuous alignment and adaptation with the developers’ customers. This is expressed in the 12 principles behind Agile Manifesto, here presented in Box 4.

¹³ <https://agilemanifesto.org/>

Box 4. *Principles behind the Agile Manifesto*

1. *Our highest priority is to satisfy the customer through early and continuous delivery of valuable software.*
2. *Welcome changing requirements, even late in development. Agile processes harness change for the customer's competitive advantage.*
3. *Deliver working software frequently, from a couple of weeks to a couple of months, with a preference to the shorter timescale.*
4. *Business people and developers must work together daily throughout the project.*
5. *Build projects around motivated individuals. Give them the environment and support they need, and trust them to get the job done.*
6. *The most efficient and effective method of conveying information to and within a development team is face-to-face conversation.*
7. *Working software is the primary measure of progress.*
8. *Agile processes promote sustainable development. The sponsors, developers, and users should be able to maintain a constant pace indefinitely.*
9. *Continuous attention to technical excellence and good design enhances agility.*
10. *Simplicity – the art of maximizing the amount of work not done – is essential.*
11. *The best architectures, requirements, and designs emerge from self-organising teams.*
12. *At regular intervals, the team reflects on how to become more effective, then tunes and adjusts its behaviour accordingly.*

Agile piloting

Being a highly successful and widely applied working method in software development, fostering a number of methodologies (e.g. SCRUM) with associated experts (and certifications), Agile has been adopted in various other fields over the past decades, with methodologies proposed in various domains, including the public sector. Its function is to accelerate innovation, by experimenting in smaller scale new services and products before actual deployment in production. It is clear to see its relevance for co-design efforts including several stakeholders, particularly in urban settings, as those expressed in projects like OrganiCity and SynchroniCity. Yet, during CommuniCity, reservations emerged whether this is the most suitable method for tech innovations with marginalised groups. "Agile piloting"¹⁴ is a specific methodology developed by Forum Virium Helsinki in 2019, and introduced to the CommuniCity project.

¹⁴ "The Pocket Book for Agile Piloting", <https://forumvirium.fi/en/publication/the-pocket-book-for-agile-piloting/>

Critical commentaries on Agile

Hidden labour. Some authors argue that methods like Agile promote a digital transformation agenda in organizations that hold idealized, almost magic or utopian expectations of Agile, associating it with promises of unmatched efficiency, flexibility, and simplicity (Fugl-Meyer, 2023¹⁵; Mergel et al., 2018¹⁶). Fugl-Meyer differentiates between "agile" methods, which are specific frameworks and tools, and "Agile," representing the underlying philosophy and mindset that drive broader organizational change beyond particular techniques. Besides, as in the case of contemporary AI developments, there are hidden costs and hidden labour behind innovation processes which are commonly overlooked for the primary focus on results. This has been confirmed in our observations: Agile piloting aims to deliver tools, but overlooks the opportunity of narrating and addressing complexities of the innovation processes. At the time of writing this report, the project communicated on its website and its social media mostly success stories of the pilots, with less emphasis on the various behind-the-scenes efforts involving city administrations, innovation companies, knowledge institutions, jury members, and others. Specifically, it tended to overlook sharing a narrative about the complexity of the process itself, including the obstacles and challenges faced along the way, even though these insights could be quite valuable. This might suggest a somewhat simplified perspective, implying that the costs of a single technological pilot "solution" are limited to just the 12.5k EUR grant, which could potentially underestimate the full extent of the efforts required.

Depoliticization of processes. The application of software development methods (i.e. *Agile*) into processes that intrinsically concern the *polis* tends to depoliticize them, making them possibly less complex within policy circles and for the general public. This attitude is expressed for instance in the process of renaming participating actors through roles (project manager, pilot host, pilot teams, target groups).

Critical scholars, specifically those of STS tradition, however, see every project of technology building as a socio-technical and political process marked with stakeholders' interests and power imbalances. Authors as Ryghaug and Skjølsvold

¹⁵ Ann Fugl-Meyer. The Agile Imperative: A Qualitative Study of a Translation Process in the Danish Tax Administration. PhD Thesis, Copenhagen Business School, Denmark, 2023

¹⁶ Ines Mergel, Yiwei Gong, and John Bertot. Agile government: Systematic literature review and future research. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(2):291–298, 2018.

(2021)¹⁷ articulated a critique towards the idea of "piloting society" who looked at pilot and demonstration projects as pivotal modes of innovation in contemporary transitions. According to the authors, such projects serve as significant political arenas for shaping future socio-technical orders. Therefore, it is of immense importance to implement these processes in the right way.

Possible responses

In the light of these commentaries, it is important to gain and keep the capacity to critically consider Agile principles. For doing this, we need to retake the fundamental distinction between **technical intervention** vs **socio-technical intervention**. Agile methods, as applied in the "Agile piloting process" utilized in CommuniCity, frames socio-technical interventions as primarily technical, both from a process point of view and from an ideological perspective. Or the other way around, if the framing we apply to see the world is primarily technical, Agile piloting is likely the best option we have to intervene. This could be read in CommuniCity from the processes that are tech oriented in their terminology, focus and results.

Yet, projects like CommuniCity, with its aim to serve marginalised communities, invite for reconsidering tech innovation as primarily a socio-technical transition. An uncritical application of Agile when solving complex societal challenges would result in innovation models that exhibit top-down, more powerful actors-driven innovation.

First, with respect to hidden labour, it is extremely important to capture by-design all the amount of valuable work invested to bring these 101 tools in CommuniCity to the world. Just as acting against the mystification of AI, it is crucial to highlight the human effort behind the technology development that is intended to make our lives easier¹⁸. In this sense, documenting and publishing the efforts of various participants in innovation endeavours is essential, alongside celebrating technological tools and achieved results.

Second, it has to be recognized that the emphasis on efficiency, short time-frame, and effectiveness upon limited budgets obfuscates the need for long-term processes of **community-trust building**. Making public stories of challenges and perseverance

¹⁷ Ryghaug, M., Skjølsvold, T.M. (2021). Transforming Society Through Pilot and Demonstration Projects. In: Pilot Society and the Energy Transition. Palgrave Pivot, Cham.

¹⁸ Crawford, K. (2021). The Atlas of AI: Power, Politics, and the Planetary Costs of Artificial Intelligence. Yale University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1ghv45t>

throughout difficult co-creation sessions available in the reports of tech developers in section 1.2, could create a great contribution to the public debate on complexity of technology transition in public interest. As observed in the literature, there are clear contradictions between the depoliticized understandings of community (as target users) and the types of community engagement and participation that are to be found in disadvantaged communities¹⁹.

The CommuniCity Agile Piloting Process has proven to manage to achieve its ambitious goals with rapid acceleration. Given the constraints, the model demonstrated capacities for learning through incremental improvement. As we will explore in the next chapter, the current innovation model tends to support certain co-creation formats (“for” and “with”) more than others (“by”), which could open up opportunities for marginalized communities to play a more active role in guiding the innovation process.

2.4 Knowledge from case studies

In this section, we will provide more detailed information on a few selected cases of co-creation occurring during Round 3, marked as successful, proposed and reasoned by piloting managers from different cities. Case studies are analysed through the following dimensions:

- **leadership**: who is initiating and leading co-creation;
- **focus**: either product/service or process;
- **target group participants**: individual user, group of individual users, civil society representing marginalised communities, public service handling questions of marginalised communities;
- **ownership**: who owns (in terms of material and immaterial assets) the solution (product and/or process);
- **decision making**: either led individually or jointly.
- **legacy**: what may be the long-standing effects of the pilots.

2.4.1 Case study 1 - Engage Manchester - Tech-Enabled Community Action with Commu App

¹⁹ Hancock, L., Mooney, G., & Neal, S. (2012). Crisis social policy and the resilience of the concept of community. *Critical Social Policy*, 32(3), 343–364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018312444410>

Pilot has been developed in the third round of piloting of CommuniCity, within the so called “wildcard” challenge formulated by the city of Manchester as following: *“How can technology support Manchester’s Food Partnership?”*. The target group for this challenge was defined as *“Our Manchester Food Partnership and nonprofits under that umbrella”*. Pilot is supported by two persons from the Manchester city administration in the form of familiarizing tech developers with the local context and providing contacts. The tech developer applying for the challenge is Commu, a Finnish start-up that has developed a digital platform, a Commu app, they refer to as *“Tinder for Good Deeds”*. A platform is designed to connect people within local communities by providing an online space to request and offer help for everyday needs. Support ranges from running errands, offering companionship, or sharing practical skills. In the Manchester pilot, Commu was adapted to increase cooperation between organisations and manage volunteer activities for the local food-bank network. The objective of co-creation activities was to adapt a tool that directly addressed local needs. The Commu App already had more than 100,000 users with more than 35,000 good deeds recorded and more than 30 city customers on it. In CommuniCity, it was the first time for Commu that they got to really focus on marginalised communities.

Figure 14. Screenshot of the Commu app interface

Karoliina Kauhanen, a representative of the tech-developer, says that it was very important for their company to have personal meetings in the Manchester context, which they learned about through information by the civil servants from the municipality. However, physical meetings with the local non-profit partners have opened more avenues for action and better adaptation to the local needs contributing, according to

Karoliina, to trust building before all. Although this solution already existed, and it was basically applied to a new city's context in Manchester, it should be considered not as "co-creation for" as it is not focused on an individual user, but it empowers community building through collaboration and voluntary work (promoting values different than individualistic orientation), not solving an individual person's issue (disability) as presented in other cases.

What distinguishes this pilot project lies in its focus on creating and strengthening connections within the community among various stakeholders—networking non-profit organizations and volunteers, existing community infrastructure with individuals who are not familiar with it, and establishing non-monetary links among individuals, as well as promoting the values of helping and doing good deeds. Pilot is focusing on strengthening existing and enabling new communities' ties, which last for a long time. It is a free app available to all, and its funding model is based on partnering with cities who pay their subscription for utilizing the app as a community communication platform. Pilot is supporting the public interest and aligns with the public values of the city administrations. Karolina points out that the city of Manchester now wants to implement a citywide solution on Commu. They want the entire food bank network and later the entire City of Manchester to join the app to make asking for help and giving help easier for citizens. Starting with the food banks within the CommuniCity pilot was an important step due to the urgency of the problem.

An additional aspect in this pilot is related to its promotional activities. Promoting stories of people and organisations supporting ones in need contributes to the stimulation of humanistic and community-oriented values in the public sphere, contributing to the sense of belonging, cohesion and resilience in the city.

2.4.2 Case study 2- Sensory Engagement Program Helsinki

The Sensory Engagement Program pilot was implemented by a small Finnish tech-developer Kelosound Oy / TUNTU in the third round of piloting in the CommuniCity project, targeting patients in psychiatric or rehabilitative care who would benefit from tailored, smoothing sensory experiences. The pilot based its approach on the notion that nature sounds have a measurable calming effect on patients and can support emotional regulation even in acute care settings.

Data collected in the final report of the Sensory Engagement Program provide a rich description of the piloting process and the role of the co-creation.

This pilot focused on creating multisensory, calming environments for a psychiatric hospital in Finland by integrating sound, light, and nature-based design. The main objective was to support the wellbeing of patients, particularly those from marginalised or vulnerable groups, by transforming two patient rooms into emotionally resonant, inclusive spaces. The co-creation process involved multiple sessions with hospital staff, including nurses and doctors familiar with the needs of individuals with mental health conditions and cognitive impairments. Mood boards, colour palettes, and spatial concepts were developed collaboratively and approved by the team before implementation. Stakeholders contributed valuable insights to ensure the solutions were functional, accessible, and aligned with therapeutic goals. The final implementation includes immersive soundscapes, ambient lighting, and natural materials, all carefully selected to reduce stress and enhance comfort. Early feedback from staff and patients has been positive, indicating increased relaxation and a more welcoming atmosphere in the rooms. Next steps include monitoring user experiences over time and offering the hospital a proposal to retain the installations permanently. The pilot demonstrates the impact of co-designed, sensory-based environments in mental health settings.

Kirsi Ihalainen, CEO of Kelosound Oy / TUNTU lead of pilot Sensory Engagement Program implemented in Helsinki claims that through the experience of CommuniCity she has learned that there is an alarming need for the kind of solution that her company proposed. Beside this, Ihalainen says that she learned to work more closely with the personnel of the psychiatric ward and find a perfect way to create and implement her pilot.

During the pilot, the team collected answers from the personnel about their and the patients experiences anonymously through internet forms they created. With regards to co-creation activities, Ihalainen points out that their team has collaborated closely with the hospital staff to understand what kind of implementations they would like to see in the rooms. Based on these discussions, they created mood boards and colour palettes for both spaces, which the staff reviewed and approved. After reaching a shared vision,

Ihalainen proceeded to source the right partners and subcontractors to bring the designs to life according to their plans. The co-creation process included several planning sessions with approximately 5–10 hospital staff members, representing both medical and administrative roles, and took place on-site at the hospital. The valuable co-creation activity was making questionnaires for the personnel, in order to learn how the spaces were used and how people reacted to them.

Through the team's focus on creating calming, inclusive, and accessible spaces within the hospital that benefits all patients, regardless of background or cognitive state, they ensured positive experience for the participants from marginalised communities. Nature-based design, sensory elements, and ease of use have been key principles throughout. By co-creating with hospital professionals who work directly with patients from marginalised or vulnerable groups (such as people with mental health conditions or cognitive impairments), Ihalainen's team have ensured that the environments support wellbeing, dignity, and comfort.

The team maintained a strong culture of ethical awareness by closely collaborating with hospital staff who have daily contact with patients from marginalised or vulnerable backgrounds. Their expertise and insights guided the pilot team in making ethically sound design decisions that respect the dignity, privacy, and diverse needs of all users. Ihalainen notes that her team also prioritised transparency, consent, and safety throughout the process, ensuring that no sensitive data was collected and that all design choices served the wellbeing of the patients above all else.

Ihalainen regards co-creation sessions as essential in ensuring that the final outcome truly reflected the needs of the target group. By working closely with hospital staff, who have first-hand experience with the patients, her team was able to gain deep insight into the daily challenges and emotional needs of different user groups. Their input directly influenced the design choices, materials, functionality, and overall atmosphere of the spaces, resulting in a solution that feels intuitive, calming, and supportive for both patients and staff.

Ihalainen mentions that one barrier her team encountered was related to budget limitations. Staff requested a reclining chair or sofa to improve relaxation, but due to budget constraints, the request was declined, and alternative comfort options were explored.

Based on her experience in CommuniCity, Ihalainen suggest valuable points when it comes to co-creation:

Start by truly listening. Co-creation is not about offering ready-made solutions but building something together. When working with institutions like hospitals, collaborate closely with the staff who know the users best. Visual tools such as mood boards, sketches, and colour palettes can help communicate ideas clearly and engage participants early on. Also, be prepared for change: flexibility and openness are key when working with different stakeholders. Finally, invest time in building trust, it lays the foundation for a successful and respectful collaboration.

This pilot was distinct among others developed in CommuniCity because it did not represent a technological solution in the literal meaning, and supporting such a pilot suggests flexibility of piloting partners to understand innovation as a socio-technical process in which pure technological solutions sometimes cannot respond to the complexity of the social problems. Furthermore, the pilot clearly describes the importance of genuine collaboration within the co-creation process between the tech-party, staff at the public psychiatric hospital Aurora Hospital in Helsinki, and the City of Helsinki (private- public-public). The process was jointly led, and all decisions were made collaboratively, resulting in the building of two prototypes of sensory rooms.

Aims of the pilot team is that the room prototypes developed remain in public domain for a long period (ideally indefinitely) after the pilot is finalized. In this way the selected pilot contributed to the building a public value for all in need, resulting in joint ownership by TUNTU (technology developer, owns the final rights), Forum Virium Helsinki, and City of Helsinki.

Figure 15a. Nature Room 1: Honkain haiku (“Haiku of the Pines”) is located in the closed psychiatric ward 7 of Aurora Hospital. Intended uses: Calming patients and reducing

Figure 15b. Nature Room 2: Kedon kehto (“Meadow’s Cradle”) is located in the psychiatric emergency unit of Aurora Hospital and functions as a seclusion room.

anxiety, staff meetings, and doctor–patient consultations. Intended use: Calming and soothing patients.

2.4.3 Case study 3- Discover Campanhã: Your AI-Driven Guide to Local Life in Porto

“Discover Campanhã” is a community-focused digital platform that consolidates social services, job opportunities, local initiatives, and support for residents in this Porto community. The pilot's goal was to help marginalized groups by offering centralized access to key information and resources to encourage social inclusion. According to tech-developer of this pilot, co-creation activities played an important role in shaping the platform to meet real user needs. Feedback was collected through meetings, user testing, and design reviews to ensure accessibility and relevance. Collaboration with a civic partner, the Association of the Cerebral Palsy Porto (APPC), was essential for the success of co-creation activities. We have conducted an interview with Fábio Guedes and Filipa Luz, from APPC to capture their experience from the CommuniCity piloting process.

ACCP is a nonprofit organization, 50 years old with a long tradition of work with the communities in Porto, collecting information and having partnerships in the community. Fábio Guedes, an APPC representative interviewed for this report, argues that it is essential for the organisation to have strong partnerships and network with the community to do their work properly, to have better integration in the community. Network and trust built by APPC in the Campanhã community was instrumental for bringing organisations and individuals from different marginalised communities to participate in the co-creation activities. Various groups took part- from people who are living in the social neighbourhood, children in local school to migrants, disabled people and other vulnerable communities.

Figure 16. Co-creation sessions in Porto during the pilot “Discover Campanhã”

The role of APPC was crucial in shaping the co-creation activities and bringing vulnerable communities to participate. In this pilot, their role was to facilitate co-creation from the very beginning, starting from the challenges formulation processes, design ideation to solution development. APPC was in charge of selecting locations and participants for the co-creation activities. Tech developers were, according to Fábio, very responsive to the feedback of the community members. After the co-creation sessions, they ended up with completely different point of view. Furthermore, Fábio believes that that the co-creation process was very important for people to actively participate and to get the sense of the ownership of the platform.

Fábio points out that participants of the co-creation sessions coming from the marginalised communities needed time to become truly active in these sessions. "Something that we have understood during these sessions is that there are different paces- one of the community, and another one of tech-developers. Community needs time to integrate in the process and to develop sense of ownership of the platform. It requires time. Another pace is the pace of the pilot, of the innovation project which is faster than community. Community participation should remain informal because in that case people feel more relaxed and ready to participate." Therefore, Fábio argues, allocating more time for co-creation with marginalised communities and harmonisation of these different dynamics is really important for future projects such as CommuniCity. In addition, with more time, Fábio argues, communities could have stronger demand towards the tech-developers regarding the more accurate solution.

Fábio: “We need more time for people to be more active and more integrated in the tech solution process. Pilots have a short period of time, and people in the co-creation sessions

are from different contexts so it is difficult for them to be actively participating in such a short time. If we would have more time, it would be easier to get all feedback, integrate it and to refine the tool”.

Besides time, Fábio highlights the need for resources for civil society organisations that participate in such a tech-innovation processes. These small organisations have not many resources, and it is difficult for them be actively participating in all sessions. If they would have more time, people could organise themselves to participate more actively, concludes Fábio.

Being involved in the innovation process from the beginning until the end, with strong say regarding the co-creation processes, APPC embedded a strong sense of ownership. However, Fábio thinks that the material ownership and the governance of the developed tool should be shared. He points out that it is good that the solution is stored at the server of the Municipality of Porto. Fábio appreciates the fact that there is an idea to create some kind of consortia to further develop and maintain the solution after the end of the CommuniCity project. Filipa, Fábio's colleague from APPC stresses that this solution will only work if several organisations and local communities continue contributing to its content. Otherwise, it is impossible to know what is happening in the community without a community. She believes that it is important to have some sort of thinking exercise with other stakeholders to decide together on how to maintain the solution. “To answer the question how to continue this solution after CommuniCity, we would need Porto Digital and the tech company to think with us”, points Filipa. Fábio believes that co-ownership is the best option that will make solution last in time. Here, he returns to the issue of resources of civil society organisations and the need to build their capacities to run a platform like this one developed within CommuniCity. Furthermore, civil society organisations could have a role in promoting the platform in the community, to help people become aware that this platform exists.

Filipa: “We are a social organisation, and it is very interesting for us to be part of the creating of the technological solution with the tech-company. However, we need to think about the sustainability of the solution. In the end, we are the social organisation, and we have a lack of human resources to implement even our own projects. It is very challenging to think how we could integrate further development and maintenance of this tech platform in our daily schedule. We need to have a dialogue with tech company and the

city. Not only to build a pilot, but how to make this solution really being sustainable in the community”.

The experience of co-creation in CommuniCity could have impact on democracy, on involvement of citizens in other similar participatory processes. Filipa points out that it was very interesting to experience that people were involved, not only when the solution was ready for use, but when the solution was in construction. She thinks that this is a very special exercise and that now APPC needs to think how to give back to the community. “To show them the platform and say- look, we have integrated your ideas, your expectations, thank you for participating”. She thinks that this will create the sense of co-ownership among the people in a way that my view was important in the process, so I want to participate more in other initiatives. In addition, civil society organisations like APPC need to manage expectations of the citizens involved in co-creation processes. Fábio emphasizes that people have some expectations from the solution, they get excited about the platform, and it was difficult for APPC to balance that expectations and keep the trust and networks we build in the community. This could create an additional burden to civil society organisations that take part in the tech-innovation processes as an intermediary, and this should be acknowledged.

Finally, both Fábio and Filipa point out that they think technological innovations are exciting and relevant for marginalised communities, but it should keep strong human character. It is nice to have this platform and a chatbot which people could use to ask their questions and look for information they need. But the platform needs to have social organisations behind, otherwise they will not get all the answers they need. People will get some information, but they still need to have a social intermediary to provide them other dimensions, information, support and integration in the community. “We need to humanize the tech-innovation process”, argues Fábio. “We have technology, but we also need to have social organisations behind to support people. And we need to provide some resources for this”, says Fábio.

“We need to remember that the tech solution is never closed, it needs maintenance and adjustment”, stresses Fábio. “Civic organisations are important because they respond to people’s needs, they cannot exist without people. If you don’t have people, you don’t have civic organisations. Without people, you don’t have technologies. Otherwise, we are creating the solution which will not get the next episode”, concludes Fábio.

2.4.4 Case study 4: Access To Healthcare (A2HC) chatbot Amsterdam

The idea for the challenge and the tech tool came from a nonprofit foundation “Right to Create” which has a history of work with undocumented people, and is aware of all challenges they might face in their everyday lives. This NGO and a university researcher from the Vrije Universiteit (VU) in Amsterdam who acted as a tech-developer in this pilot are running the project together with undocumented and formerly undocumented people. Collaboration between the Right to Create was established prior to CommuniCity and now synthesized in the Access to Health Care (AC2H) chatbot.

Annette Kouwenhoven, a founder of the foundation “Right to Create” and the AC2HC chatbot pilot initiator, mentions that preparations for this tech tool have been started way before the CommuniCity pilot. “Our collaboration started while working together with the VU about four years ago where we organised tours in the city with students. We would visit together different locations where undocumented people live, and the guides through the city were undocumented people. Students would learn a lot out of this collaboration, and it made us start thinking. What kind of tools do we need for the access to healthcare? We had many brainstorming sessions, and we decided about three years ago that we should have a chatbot- I think I still have a picture of it on a post-it. So that's when we started to bring this idea across to the VU and they applied for funding that enabled us to start working together before CommuniCity”, points Annette.

Figure 11 shows one of their co-creation sessions. All decisions about changes and updates of the tool are based on the needs defined during co-creation sessions and made jointly.

Co-creation activities included representatives of undocumented people in all phases, from insights and ideation as well as other NGOs including Stap Verder, Wereldhuis, Migrante, and IMWU. Co-creation sessions have been essential in shaping a chatbot that truly reflects the needs of end-users. A key takeaway for the Right to Create foundation as a pilot lead was the importance of language – users especially valued clear, group-specific, and accessible communication, as well as transparency about how contributions of the stakeholders and NGOs shaped the bot. In 4 sessions with the different groups, Right to Create collected relevant information by and user feedback of the participants. They wanted to make sure that the app speaks the users' language and meets the needs of those most in need for reference, or explanations on the spot.

Figure 17. Co-creation session for the Access 2 Health Care ChatBot, Amsterdam

The target group of this pilot were both a group of users – undocumented people, and civil society organisations that work with their issues. Amsterdam has a vivid ecosystem of organisations focused on issues of undocumented people. This pilot connects efforts of various actors into one chatbot that offers factual information regarding the right and access to healthcare in Amsterdam for undocumented people. In this vein, the pilot empowers forming of community ties among civil society organisations that serve the undocumented people as they need to provide data/sources for the chatbot.

In regard to ownership, the A2HC chatbot is an open-source solution, anyone can use and adapt it. For now, the developer (from the university) will host/maintain it, but there is a plan that the Right to Create foundation register a separate legal body with the name of the tool and organize fundraising for future maintenance and updates of the tool under that umbrella. In that sense, the community keeps the ownership of the tool. The chatbot is ready for use but more NGOs are needed to add data/sources and let undocumented people know the chatbot exists. Right to Create foundation plan to communicate its co-creation processes through a working document called “A co-creation manifesto”. According to the foundation, the technology, for now, is already performing beyond expectations

Annette says that co-creation is not necessarily about “something creative”. It is definitely creative, laughs Annette, but above all, “it has to do with ownership and that is exactly in line with our way of working- who has the keys, who has the access? So, it is not indeed only for the tool that you develop, it is the whole background of how you actually do it, how do you manage it, and how do you make it transparent. That is the core of co-creation.” Annette emphasises that this type of co-creation- that takes into consideration the needs of undocumented people and is developed by undocumented people- needs longer timelines and flexibility because it is based on trust building.

Furthermore, Annette points out that she hopes that tech companies involved in such tech pilots realise that they are developing it for a community, so they should really get to know more on what the communities need. She believes that a mediator or similar kind of person that can facilitate these processes, a linking pin between different worlds, is crucial. If the worlds of technology and marginalised communities are linked directly, via this linking pin, the outcome is much better for all, stresses Annette.

For Annette, the key learnings from this pilot in CommuniCity were that the social and human dimension has proven more critical than the technology itself. As her foundation moves forward, their priority would be to involve more communities, adopt open-source principles that tool embodies, and amplify diverse voices – not only for this project, but for future rights-based development.

The AC2H chatbot was one of the exceptional cases where an organization from the civil society sector applied to the CommuniCity Open Call, as most applications throughout the three rounds of CommuniCity were primarily from tech developers. In this case, the challenge itself was set-up with a greater degree of shared ownership between partnering city and the nonprofit foundation Right to Create. Therefore, this case is relevant as an example that leadership in technological innovation could come from civil society organisations. Every encounter with technology development, as demonstrated by this pilot, empowers civil society to take a more active role in the technological development in the city and contributes to the democratisation of technology.

Conclusion from selected case studies

In this section we zoomed-in into four different pilot cases from the third round of the CommuniCity piloting process. This close-up analysis reveals common aspects of the co-creation processes and its relation to marginalised communities. *Collective bottom-*

up leadership as seen in the AC2H chatbot case, contributing to the creation and *strengthening of new communities* as in the Commu case, strong integration of marginalised communities in co-creation processes coordinated by civil society actor with strong network and trust within community as in the case of APPC engagement in the pilot “Discover Campanhã” in Porto, and *establishing lasting public value* over the long term as presented in the Sensory Engagement Programme, which extends well beyond the completion of the pilot. This is even more evident in the AC2H case that continues to *strengthen the community ownership* of the tech tool after CommuniCity. Pilots highlight the importance of *having a mediator* in co-creation processes, as well as *flexibility* and *longer timelines* needed for trust building between tech parties and the marginalised communities. All chosen pilots view co-creation as a *strong, long-term partnership*, with *shared ownership*, whether their funding models are public or non-profit. We believe that, as such, they can serve as a solid guidance for further exploration and conceptualization of the co-creation led “by” marginalised communities.

2.5 Knowledge from collaborating partner from WP4

Since the role of WP2 (see Figure 1 on page 17) is to research processes and participate in feedback loops with other WPs in the project, an alignment has been established between the objectives of this deliverable and a technical tool developed by our partner Computer Vision Center (CVC) from WP4. This tool, called the *Pedagogic Demonstrator*, facilitates a moment of reflection for pilot teams regarding the ethical considerations to be accounted for while building AI systems in relation to the regulations defined in the AI Act. Although most deliverables of WP2 focus on the ethical dimensions of responsible innovation (particularly relevant in the case of co-creation with marginalised communities), this contribution is relevant as it provides attention to the *technical dimension* of responsible innovation.

The general objective of WP4 is to provide a fundamental technical toolbox to support the design and development of innovative solutions to be experimented in the project pilot cities. The WP4 covers technical specifications, software components, and tools to be used by cities and tech developers to build solutions that can be interoperable and easily replicable across diverse domains and locations.

Activities of WP2 are linked to the need for reflection about the ethical concerns on how innovation processes can include (or exclude) marginalised communities. A particular

dimension of this endeavour is related to the software development processes for AI-based systems, going within the scope of the new regulatory body provided by the European AI Act. The European AI Act is a new regulatory framework which extends the European Single Market regulatory body for products and services using AI-based systems, aiming at the protection of the consumer, and ensuring that AI systems are developed and used responsibly. In this context, the reflection activity is not perceived uniquely as a *posteriori* validation for the proposed systems, but as an *ex-ante* action to be taken care of during the co-creation phase, focus of CommuniCity's pilots.

Within this framing, the Computer Vision Center (CVC) has developed the Pedagogic Demonstrator presented in Box 4.

Box 5. CommuniCity Pedagogic Demonstrator, a reflective tool for pilot teams to familiarize with the features of European AI Act

In order to illustrate how to implement a self-assessment process supporting a responsible development of AI-based tools, the CVC team curated an interactive demonstrator for educational and demonstrative purposes, which is described within the context of the D5.2, and that can be accessed through this link:

<https://www.cvc.uab.es/communi-city-demonstrator-facial-expressions-and-generative-ai>.

The target prototype consists of an installation which illustrates how artificial intelligence can recognize human expressions and translate them into artistic representations, using a number of software components from the CommuniCity

Toolbox (Detection of faces in an image or video, Recognition of facial expressions in an image or video). The demonstrator provides an extensive contextualization of the prototype within the new regulatory framework of the European AI Act in an interactive web page with multimedia contents, which can be accessed openly.

For the ethical and legal assessment applied through this demonstrator, a collaborative effort has been established between the Computer Vision Center (CVC) and the *Observatory for Ethics in Artificial Intelligence of Catalonia* (OEIAC) (<https://oeiac.cat/en>). The self-assessment tool used for the analysis was the PIO Model (<https://oeiac.cat/en/the-pio-model/>), developed by the OEIAC which addresses ethical and legal uses, and which is harmonised with legislative requirements and current ethical standards and recommendations. This assessment tool consists of a checklist on ethical uses structured around seven principles, and designed for the development, deployment and evaluation of AI data and systems.

The development of this prototype suggested that further interactions may be considered between the social and technical dimensions. For instance, the AI Act particularly pays relevant attention to the mitigation of the potential biases induced by the datasets used for training machine learning systems, which are not always analyzed under the light of balanced characteristics for features such as gender, skin colour, age, and other. These features may be directly or indirectly linked to underrepresented sections of the population, and particularly linked to those not (initially) perceived as potential candidates for the final products, services or processes. Supporting the self-assessment action additional tools and methodologies for bias analysis and mitigation may further promote the values and principles underlying the AI Act, as well as CommuniCity's aims.

3. Co-creation challenges and possible pathways

In the previous chapter, the concept of co-creation was systematically mapped through an analysis of knowledge generated within the deliverables of WP2, complemented by empirical data derived from surveys of technology developers, observation of the Agile piloting process and an examination of selected case studies. The current chapter

adopts a broader perspective, drawing upon the extant academic literature to contextualize and deepen the understanding of co-creation within a wider theoretical framework. The chapter concludes with a list of guidelines for piloting and co-creation with marginalised communities, based on collective learnings from the CommuniCity project and wider theoretical insights.

3.1 Co-creation for-with-by: the problem of definitions

3.1.1. Participatory design

Originating from Scandinavian design initiatives involving workers in the 1970s²⁰, *Participatory Design* puts in the foreground the crucial role of users in the design of information and communication technologies, emphasizing the situational expertise of people and democratic ideals^{21,22}. At a fundamental level, Participatory Design is defined as a process that fosters mutual learning among participants through collective “reflection-in-action.” Participants typically engage in dual roles as users and designers, with designers seeking to understand the users’ realities while users articulate their goals and identify suitable technological means to achieve them.²³ From this tradition comes also the phrase “for- with- by-” which refers to different perspectives on designing organisational and technological systems.^{24,25}

Although a relatively small area of research and practice, *community-based co-creation* emerged already within the Participatory Design movement and gained significance with the ongoing trends of deeper integration of information technologies

²⁰ E. Bjorgvinsson, P. Ehn, and P.-A. Hillgren, “Participatory design and “democratising innovation”” in Proceedings of the 11th Biennial participatory design conference, 2010, pp. 41–50.

²¹ E.B.-N.Sanders and P.J.Stappers, “Co-creation and the new landscapes of design,” *Co-design*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 5–18, 2008.

²² Ertner, A. M. Kragelund, and L. Malmborg, “Five enunciations of empowerment in participatory design,” in Proceedings of the 11th Biennial Participatory Design Conference, 2010, pp. 191–194.

²³ Robertson, T., & Simonsen, J. (2012). Participatory Design: An introduction. In *Routledge International Handbook of Participatory Design* (pp. 1-18). Routledge. <http://www.routledge.com/books/details/9780415694407/>

²⁴ *ibidem*.

²⁵ DiSalvo, C., A. Clement and V. Pipek (2012). Communities- Participatory Design for, with and by communities in Simonsen, J. and Robertson, T. (Eds.) (2012). *Routledge International Handbook of Participatory Design* (pp. 182- 209). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203108543>.

into daily life, resulting in the recognition of the importance of social services and civil society (NGOs, citizens) as partners in the participative design efforts. These non-profit organisations usually tackle important societal issues such as environmental protection, sustainable development, historical preservation, the arts, healthcare, food distribution, low-income housing, animal protection, and public safety. In this vein, Participatory Design developed a cluster that engages with communities through practices of cultural production aiming to facilitate creative and critical discovery through the arts, while also acknowledging that these cultural production forms promote learning and often serve as politicised acts²⁶.

3.1.2. Co-creation

Despite its historical roots in participatory design, the concept of “co-creation” extends today across various fields, involving multiple types of stakeholders, and yet, it lacks clear practical guidelines. Usually, it is associated with the involvement of diverse actors from civil society, academia, policy, and industry to collectively address challenges related to sustainability or innovation²⁷.

The CommuniCity project had adopted a definition of co-creation proposed by the consortium partner ENOLL, and included it in its documents and official website²⁸:

Co-creation is a collaborative process that brings together various stakeholders, such as public authorities, industry representatives, researchers, customers, and end beneficiaries, including community groups. These stakeholders jointly develop solutions, products, or ideas. Instead of being a unilateral process led by a company or a public administration, co-creation actively involves all interested parties, leveraging their unique perspectives and knowledge.

The fundamental idea behind co-creation is that collaboration among different stakeholders leads to more equal, innovative, relevant, and tailored solutions that better address the needs and expectations of the target audience. This process

²⁶ ibidem.

²⁷ J.Herberg, The critique of co-creation: Democratic dialogue or displaced politics?, in: F. Kluge(Ed.), Transdisciplinarity: A Research Mode for Real-World Problems, Population Europe Secretariat, 2022.

²⁸ <https://communicity-project.eu/faqs/>

can be applied in various contexts, from product design and service development to the creation of public policies and business strategies.

In a more general form, co-creation can be defined as a collaborative approach to *creative problem-solving*, involving diverse stakeholders, ideally at all stages, and on equal terms. At the kick-off of the project, based on this problem-solving-oriented formulation, we sketched a rough distinction between three forms of co-creation, depending on the configuration of the ownership of the problem and of the solution.

- In **co-creation for**, we preliminarily proposed, the solution already exists, it is adapted/tested on the target group.
- In **co-creation with**, the problem is given, but the solution is designed together with a target group.
- In **co-creation by**, the problem-setting itself is led by the target group.

Even if simplistic, this framework is sufficiently expressive to show e.g. structural limitations in the piloting model, as long as the challenges were set-up upfront by other actors than the target group.

In D2.3 we investigated in more detail the history associated with the use of the term “co-creation”, reorganising dedicated literature on the subject. We concluded that co-creation in the context of smart cities (as well as other “co-” terminologies) can lead to misinterpretations among various stakeholders²⁹. Indeed, awareness about the ambiguity of co-creation was observed in the project consortia after the first round of piloting and, even if consequent actions have been developed to address it, different views on the character of co-creation have persisted across the project and the various participants.

3.1.3. Marginalised groups

Community gets everywhere and seems to survive everything. It has become something of a sociological given that using the concept of community is asking for trouble.

(Hancock & Mooney, 2012.)

²⁹ *ibidem*.

The typically low-intensity and varied activities associated with citizen participation pose challenges for engaging marginalised communities in smart city initiatives³⁰. The issue of the so-called “pseudo-participation”³¹ is particularly pronounced when attempting to involve marginalised groups in technological innovations in cities. But what defines *marginalised groups*?

In the literature, as well as across our partners during the project, we observed two different meanings associated to “group”:

- groups as **user segments** of the population, i.e. individuals sharing similar attributes/needs, potential service consumers.
- groups as **communities**, i.e. informal social structures, composed not only by individuals, but also by shared practices, norms, values, history.

The first meaning is suitable to the usual framing for *co-creation for* and *co-creation with* initiatives. The second is required for a *co-creation by*, as setting the agenda requires some form of collective agency, that only communities own. Yet, CommuniCity is distinct from previous projects particularly because it aims to engage with marginalised groups.

The literature frequently talks about *marginalisation* in connection with inclusion and social exclusion without providing explicit definitions³². Despite ambiguity, ‘marginalisation’ often transforms into related concepts like disadvantage, discrimination, disempowerment, exclusion, inequality, silencing, stigmatisation, victimisation, and more³³. Razer et al. define social exclusion as a state in which individuals or groups lack effective participation in key activities or benefits of the society

³⁰ H. Smith, G. M. Medero, S. Crane De Narváez, W. Castro Mera, Exploring the relevance of ‘smart city’ approaches to low-income communities in Medellín, Colombia, *GeoJournal* 88 (2023) 17–38.

³¹ F. Delgado, S. Yang, M. Madaio, Q. Yang, The participatory turn in AI design: Theoretical foundations and the current state of practice, in: *Proceedings of the 3rd ACM Conference on Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization*, EAAMO '23, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2023. doi:10.1145/3617694.3623261.

³² K. Messiou, Collaborating with children in exploring marginalisation: an approach to inclusive education, *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 16 (2012) 1311–1322. doi:10.1080/13603116.2011.572188.

³³ D. Gurnham, Introduction: marginalisation in law, policy and society, *International Journal of Law in Context* 18 (2022) 1–9. doi:10.1017/S1744552322000027.

in which they live³⁴. Social exclusion involves being marginalised from society, encompassing feelings of alienation, undervaluation, and incapacity to contribute meaningfully to the community³⁵. The critical smart city scholars therefore argue for developing power-balanced relationships in participatory design, by exploring new ways of engaging with marginalised communities, focusing on horizontal processes and the changing role of designers³⁶. Yet, as powerfully observed by Reuter: *“marginalised communities—such as racial, religious, and ethnic minorities; women; migrants and refugees; persons with disabilities; the elderly; the LGBTQ community; and people living in poverty—[...] lack agency to become stakeholders in the urban design process [...]; their existence is often neglected and their needs remain unheard.”*³⁷ The ability of marginalised communities to take part in the smart cities processes is additionally hindered by what goes under the umbrella term “digital divide”³⁸, as well as other relevant dimensions such as linguistic divide, socio-economic divide, representation imbalance, etc.

3.2 Seeing co-creation by the lens of ownership?

During our research, we acknowledged that the initial implicit understanding of “co-creation” in terms of problem→ solution was rather limited, although easy to be aligned to software development/project management terminology. Any socio-technical intervention consists also of a process, of a product, but also expertise, support, resources, and occurs in a specific societal context, with its history, structures, tendencies, and perspectives.

³⁴ V. J. F. Michal Razer, B. Warshofsky, Schools as agents of social exclusion and inclusion, *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 17 (2013) 1152–1170. doi:10.1080/13603116.2012.742145.

³⁵ J. G. Mowat, Towards a new conceptualisation of marginalisation, *European Educational Research Journal* 14 (2015) 454–476. doi:10.1177/1474904115589864..

³⁶ F. Tomasini Giannini, I. Mulder, Towards a power-balanced participatory design process, in: *Proceedings of the Participatory Design Conference 2022 – Volume 2, PDC '22*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2022, p. 111–117. doi:10.1145/3537797.3537819.

³⁷ Kempin Reuter, T. (2019). Human rights and the city: Including marginalised communities in urban development and smart cities. *Journal of Human Rights*, 18, 382 – 402.

³⁸ J. A. van Dijk, Digital divide research, achievements and shortcomings, *Poetics* 34 (2006) 221–235. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.poetic.2006.05.004.

Figure 18. Levels of participation in tech development processes. Results from coding 80 research articles. (source: Delgado et al. 2023³⁹)

Delgado et al.⁴⁰ provided a richer conceptualization of participation in tech development based on the three dimensions *Goal*, *Scope*, and *Form* of participation, and used it to review contributions presented in the literature (see Figure 18). They discovered that the majority of participation attempts in tech development remain on the level of *consultation*. In consultation, the participation goal is generally to improve the user experience; participants are recruited by the stakeholders, and the participation is reduced to giving input on design ideas via questionnaires and interviews. Similar trends have been observed in CommuniCity (see the analysis of survey data in chapter 2), although the data shows that the incremental adjustments implemented in the process have brought some improvement.

³⁹ F.Delgado, S.Yang, M.Madaio, Q.Yang, The participatory turn in ai design: Theoretical foundations and the current state of practice, in: Proceedings of the 3rd ACM Conference on Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization, EAAMO '23, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2023. doi:10.1145/3617694.3623261.

⁴⁰ *ibidem*.

At further inspection, we can observe that the three dimensions “for- with- by-” converge to a common core. First: *which people are the target of the co-design effort?* Then, after defining these participants, we can ask, *which ownership do they have?*

Ownership is a concept that has been touched in the analysis of the surveys, and of the case studies. Furthermore, also the conceptual framework applied by Delgado et al. can be seen as expressing degrees of ownership on different dimensions: motives/values (why is participation needed?), stakes/goals (what is on the table?), initiation/participation (who is involved?), process (what form does stakeholder participation take?).

This seems to confirm that the best way to categorize the form of participation expressed by a certain pilot is by judging the various roles of ownership in it. This correlates with the extent people can identify their contribution and feel the benefit from their contribution; it involves perceiving who owns the product, the outcomes and the process. In successful cases of co-creation, it is intuitive that the marginalised community should have strong levels of attachment and perceive to benefit from the product and/or resulting process. Indeed, literature on co-creation discusses how important ownership is, because this is how the benefits of co-creation are distributed.⁴¹

While examining the surveys, we have started developing a preliminary model of the most relevant categories for describing ownership in a co-design process. At a fundamental level, ownership is conceptualized through physical, conceptual, and collective arrangement dimensions (see Fig. 19).

The physical dimension concerns *access*, that may be inflected both in material terms (e.g. possession) or in functional terms (e.g. re-use, development, maintenance). The conceptual dimension concerns *perception*, i.e. how parties interpret their contribution and feel ownership/control. These feelings may be inflected at emotional or a socio-cultural level, may interact with a sense of identity or belonging, or trigger specific psychological traits. Finally, the collective arrangement dimension concerns *legal* or para-legal aspects, which may be related to agreements, to data governance, to Intellectual Property (of algorithm, of data) involved, and related economic benefits.

⁴¹ van Rijn, H., & Stappers, P. J. (2008). Expressions of ownership: motivating users in a co-design process. In *PDC* (Vol. 8, pp. 178-81).

Figure 19. Types of ownership in the piloting and co-creation process (preliminary model)

Although initial, this framework is still a relevant contribution in this document, for at least two reasons. First, it offers a basis to formulate more precise questions for surveys to the stakeholders in future co-creation initiatives. More importantly, it provides an example of how going beyond the discussion of what “co-creation” means by pinpointing to more concrete and accessible dimensions to all participants.

3.3 Recommendations and guidelines

Based on research and knowledge produced in the deliverables of WP2, the following main findings were established throughout different phases of the CommuniCity project implementation:

- Co-creation is a complex process seen differently by different stakeholders.
- Special considerations have to be developed in co-creation activities with marginalised communities- tools, frameworks, critical questions and reflective models can support initiators of co-creation.

- Reflection is a key concept that dominated all deliverables of the WP2. Therefore, several tools, both practical and speculative, have been developed to assist in the co-creation processes.
- Ethical considerations are crucial when dealing with marginalised communities and deliverables of WP2 offers learnings and guidelines in that matter.

Grounded on the knowledge and learnings from the CommuniCity project, following practical guidelines for expanding co-creation with marginalised communities could be easily implemented within the framework of the current CommuniCity piloting model:

3.3.1. Collect data from marginalised groups

Ethics is not only about compliance. Take care of epistemological gaps. Ethics in the complex innovation processes does not concern only compliances with the existing or new frameworks or guidelines. The whole process of the tech innovation has to be critically assessed to avoid epistemological fallacies, i.e. missing to record and take into account various knowledges.

Capture data from all stakeholders in the piloting process. An evident gap in the present data collection strategy, particularly relevant if the purpose is engaging with marginalised communities, is to set up systematic efforts for capturing opinions and attitudes of marginalised communities, in various phases of the innovation process. Furthermore, to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges within urban innovation processes, and to implement these processes properly, the methodology should involve systematic collection of opinions and perspectives from civil servants involved in the piloting, as well as feedback from the general public and media within local communities.

3.3.2. Involve marginalised communities in decision-making

Involve all stakeholders in the decision-making processes in all process phases, and communicate stories around this in local communities. This can, indirectly, empower communities and encourage them to participate in such technological innovation projects and similar initiatives without fear and with prior knowledge. Documenting and publishing stories about these joint sessions among communities, tech developers,

fundors and city administration should be publicly available, would be very beneficial in that regard.

However, acknowledge that is not always possible, as experience from the CommuniCity pilots teach us. They point out the case “with psychiatric patients and dementia patients, who are unable and unwilling to contribute to the decision making (not to mention confidentiality of the patient data). This point of view highlights also the difficulties in achieving this: the most marginalised individuals are not always able to take part in the decision making. How to tackle this?”

We believe that the answer is to move beyond seeing the target groups of technological innovation in the cities as (groups of) individuals towards more organized communities either in the formal (non-profit associations or foundations) or non-formal (neighbourhood initiatives or social movements) framework. These communities represent interests of the marginalised groups and form a civil society, a space between the public sector and a market. Cities should be interested in building strong democracies and strong civil societies. Technical solutions that are focused primarily on individuals will be developed in the commercial domain nonetheless, and they should not be in focus of innovation led by local governments.

A possible way could be to start from the existing civil society initiatives and build a tech layer over it. Co-ownership is not only concerned with the ownership of the tech tool but also about shared ownership of the entire tech innovation process in cities. In the context of the CommuniCity Agile piloting process, this means the participation of marginalised communities in decision-making at every stage of the innovation process. This also includes the stage of defining the underlying assumptions or needs for a given product/service - as Delgado presents "whether and why a system should be built". In CommuniCity terms: the formulation of the open call challenges.

3.3.3. Enable and promote co-ownership

In the realm of co-creation, co-ownership would imply that marginalised communities acquire knowledge and resources of co-creation methods to independently initiate and lead co-creation processes. Additionally, this knowledge would enable them to shift from a passive tester role to an active partner in innovation processes. Minimal effort to acknowledge community ownership in the developed tech-tool could be through public communication channels that would report on the piloting process and the role of the

marginalised-community. In this way, a feeling of ownership in the marginalised communities is created, and seed for potential future tech-related endeavours planted. However, one needs to be aware that communication alone, without ensuring that the community has actual ownership through long-term or at least medium-term access to the co-produced solution, does not generate a true sense of ownership. If these dimensions are disconnected, it often reinforces a feeling of frustration, people feeling used in campaigns or social washing. In this sense, it is important to emphasize that 'access' is a prerequisite for developing any further sense of ownership. Additionally, city governments should include representatives of marginalised communities in the various presentations of the developed tech tools that would open space for establishing different relationships and networks.

However, innovation projects such as CommuniCity should also highlight the ownership of the tech tools by the cities who are the ones driving for better public services for the marginalised communities be it through public ownership or public-civic ownership. Furthermore, local governments are a critical ingredient of the process for making cities more inclusive on a policy level. This task is impossible for tech providers and communities themselves. An additional layer of ownership is related to the empowering of the city administrations to embrace digital transformations responsibly in their own organisations and services focused on marginalised communities, always remaining transparent about benefits and risks of this transformation for citizens, democracy, society and political participation. This includes embedding education programmes on AI ethics for civil servants in projects similar to CommuniCity by-design. Having the ethical teams aware of the latest developments in the domain of tech ethics and regulation should be integral to any introduction of tech innovation within the public government to mitigate unwanted situations.

3.3.4. Allocate resources for co-creation

Several interlocutors in this research have pointed out that co-creation cannot be regarded as a side activity in tech-piloting. In this regard participants involved in the CommuniCity piloting process propose to extend the piloting duration, increase the piloting budget and provide separate resources (time, budget, training) for the co-creation. Building capacities for organising and running co-creation sessions should be enhanced, not only for tech-developers, but also for all other stakeholders in this innovation project. Active stakeholders' engagement in co-creation processes, as

demonstrated in selected CommuniCity pilots, can lead to better results for all involved. Since this project put so much emphasis on co-creation, one of its key messages is that co-creation requires significant resources, including a dedicated "co-creation process mediator" on equal footing with a tech developer.

3.3.5. Do not forget reflection

The common denominator of all research endeavours of the WP2 is insight about the importance of reflection. Reflection is a prerequisite for learning and development and requires pausing for a moment to think (and pauses require time flexibility which is lacking in 6 months pilots). Learning is crucial for project-based organisations to improve and survive and reflection is essential for learning in and between projects. Research shows that these findings have two managerial implications. First, project-based organisations should give reflection-for-action a place in project work to stimulate learning in and between projects. This does not mean decoupling reflection from daily practices but rather putting more attention to reflection as an ingredient of these practices⁴².

Without WP2—a critical reflection module embedded in the CommuniCity project by-design, social learning about specific contexts of the marginalised communities would be partial. Knowledge produced based on literature reviews, processing of the data collected by stakeholders involved in the piloting process and additional research efforts, was communicated through regular knowledge feedback loops. This enabled project learning and incremental improvements in regard to co-creation throughout pilot rounds.

We demonstrated in section 2.1 how these reflective loops were provided by the researchers in WP2 in the form of project deliverables, exchanges during regular meetings of piloting beneficiaries, and other occasions. This critical reflection, based on the knowledge from literature review and collected data, were continuously processed and reflected back to the piloting partners team. The introduction of new knowledge in the running process initiated reflection and action resulting with incremental changes in

⁴² Andreas Hartmann, Joanne Vinke-de Kruijf, Ruben van Weesep (2023). Asking the right questions: The role of reflection for learning in and between projects, International Journal of Project Management, Volume 41, Issue 5, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2023.102494>.

the understanding of the complexity of innovation with marginalised communities, varied concepts of co-creation and importance of co-ownership. Here, we should not forget to mention the feedback from the "social" partners who work directly, on a daily basis, with vulnerable communities, as they contributed actively to critical feedback loops throughout piloting processes. Cumulatively, critical feedback triggered broadening of understanding in relation to co-creation for marginalised communities, changes in terminology and discourse, and finally more inclusive pilots in the last piloting round.

3.3.6 Legacy – return to the community

Leave something behind, beyond the tech tool: share knowledge, increase digital literacy level of the communities, give credits to organisations for participating in co-design processes so that they could build knowledge, portfolio and pride in the innovation/tech domain. Advocate throughout the project for the funding of education initiatives for the civil society representatives in the field of AI ethics, GDPR and data governance to empower them to safeguard ethical considerations of marginalised communities on a long run.

3.3.7. Experiment with alternative piloting models

When success of technology innovation projects is evaluated through the lens of additional dimensions—such as accountability, trust, or ownership— the concept of “success” transitions into a more relative and contextualized form. The knowledge produced by the research partners in WP2 in the CommuniCity project can serve as a foundation for developing a new methodology based on community-led innovation, which optimizes the success of technological innovations for level of trust, accountability, solidarity, dignity, and sustainability rather than primarily focusing on efficiency. An example of one such model, currently developed by Bingham et al. and presented during IEEE Ethics 2025 conference⁴³. In the preparation phase, all stakeholders discuss the following trade-offs:

⁴³ L. Bingham, L. Bruce and J. S. Kim, "ETHICS-2025 Session C4 – Workshop: Technology Training to Improve Justice for Underrepresented Populations: ETHICS-2025 Special Session, Saturday, June 7 2025, 2:45 – 4:15 PM CDT," 2025 IEEE International Symposium on Ethics in Engineering, Science, and Technology (ETHICS), Evanston, IL, USA, 2025, pp. 1-2, doi: 10.1109/ETHICS65148.2025.11098424.

- *Efficiency vs. Accountability*
- *Speed vs. Cultural/Social Sensitivity*
- *External Expertise vs. Community Control*

According to this model, all **decisions have to be made jointly** (Design Choices), with reflection on how values and various stakeholders' interests shaped the outcome. A set of questions that provide insights into community's needs during the preparation phase is presented in the Box 5:

- **Community Integrity** – Will the technology respect and preserve community knowledge?
- **Future Relevance** – Will it serve younger generations and help the community to thrive?
- **Technical Feasibility** – Can the tool be built effectively within time and budget constraints?
- **Ethical Governance** – Who controls the data? How is the technology used, and by whom?

Box 5. A set of questions to provide insight into community's needs, based on Bingham et al. 2025.

More information about the Community-Led model of innovation developed by Bingham et al., that could be inspiring and instructive when designing a community-led model is part of the *Annex 1* of this document.

Conclusion

Given the constraints of the existing piloting model, including limited budget and implementation timeframe, as stated by various stakeholders in the pilots, it could be argued that the Agile piloting model as it was carried out in CommuniCity, aimed at reaching the highly ambitious target of 100 pilot projects and, therefore, can confidently be regarded as successful, according to the perceptions of its implementers. In this way, through piloting rounds and learning loops, CommuniCity has established a distinctive framework and method for running agile pilots and open calls throughout Europe.

Nevertheless, when success is viewed through additional aspects like accountability, trust, or ownership, its evaluation becomes more nuanced and context-dependent. In this regard, the legacy of the CommuniCity project includes dedication to reflection and learning through a work package that monitored processes and conducted independent research, as well as learning loops during pilots' implementation. New knowledge and feedback produced by WP2 initiated reflection and action among partners of WP3 and WP5 resulting in incremental changes in the understanding of the complexity of innovation with marginalised communities, varied concepts of co-creation and importance of co-ownership. Furthermore, partners implementing actual pilots on-the-ground dedicated themselves to reflection and learning through many insights and lessons emerged from the reflective discussions and practice of crafting cases of more inclusive pilots. Thanks to the openness of the piloting partners to improve their practices and procedural documents (open calls, survey questions, manuals, solutions, etc.), CommuniCity managed to attain fruitful cases of meaningful engagement of marginalised communities in the technology development. Therefore, highlighting and incorporating critical feedback loops at every stage *by-design*, contributed to the model robustness and legitimation.

The CommuniCity Agile Piloting Process also provided valuable insights through the co-creation encounters between technology developers, marginalized communities, and other stakeholders such as social and public intermediaries. Although time and resources-limited, these interactions during the pilots can be seen as the beginning of something much larger—a foundation for future communities that have the potential to truly democratise technology. While this initial work is just the beginning, it offers an exciting opportunity: these seeds need care and nurturing to grow into lasting, empowered communities that can shape technology in more inclusive ways.

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ANNEX 1. Traces of the Community-Led Innovation Model optimized for trust and accountability

In the Community-Led Innovation Model, everything starts with the community, which initiates and discusses the trade-offs of introduction of the digital technologies given the fact that the funding for this project exists. Main distinctive feature of this model, according to Bingham et al. (2025)⁴⁴, are the key questions that should be asked during the preparation phase, and they are as the following:

- **Community Integrity** – Will the technology respect and preserve community knowledge?
- **Future Relevance** – Will it serve younger generations and help the community to thrive?
- **Technical Feasibility** – Can the tool be built effectively within time and budget constraints?
- **Ethical Governance** – Who controls the data? How is the technology used, and by whom?

Community representatives discuss with the tech developers, local government and the founder (be it public or private) the following trade-offs of these processes:

- *Efficiency vs. Accountability*
- *Speed vs. Cultural/Social Sensitivity*
- *External Expertise vs. Community Control*

According to this model, all decisions have to be made together (Design Choices), with reflection on how values and various stakeholders' interests shaped the outcome, in all phases of the process. Various stakeholders with various values and interests in the AI design process are shown in the table below.

⁴⁴ L. Bingham, L. Bruce and J. S. Kim, "ETHICS-2025 Session C4 - Workshop: Technology Training to Improve Justice for Underrepresented Populations: ETHICS-2025 Special Session, Saturday, June 7 2025, 2:45 - 4:15 PM CDT," 2025 IEEE International Symposium on Ethics in Engineering, Science, and Technology (ETHICS), Evanston, IL, USA, 2025, pp. 1-2, doi: 10.1109/ETHICS65148.2025.11098424.

Participant at the table	Perspectives, values, goals of the participant
Funder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goal: Support a successful, scalable, and replicable project. ● Concerned about budget alignment with available resources and long-term return on investment. ● Wants assurance that the technology will deliver measurable results. ● Interested in innovation but wary of unproven solutions. ● Cares about community outcomes, but from a metrics and sustainability lens. ● Statement: “In my role, I need to advocate for financial responsibility and push for a model that can be replicated elsewhere”.
Community Member 1 – Youth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Future-oriented and passionate about language revitalization. ● Embraces new technology as a pathway to cultural survival. ● Concerned that elders’ voices are respected but fears stagnation if nothing changes. ● Values innovation, access, and being heard in decision-making processes. ● Value Statement: “In my role, I need to advocate for bold solutions and ensure youth perspectives are part of the conversation”.
Community Member 2 – Elder 1 (Tech-Positive)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Holds deep cultural knowledge and wants to ensure traditions survive through modern tools. ● Curious and open to learning how technology can support language. ● Sees opportunity for teaching future generations through digital means. ● Values intergenerational connection and cultural evolution. ● Value Statement: “In my role, I need to support responsible tech use and encourage collaboration between generations”.

<p>Community Member 3 – Elder 2 (Tradition-Focused)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deeply rooted in tradition and cautious of change. ● Concerned about how AI might distort or commodify sacred language. ● Sceptical about outside influence and long-term cultural impacts. ● Values cultural sovereignty, oral transmission, and community-led efforts. ● Value Statement: “In my role, I need to voice concerns about preserving integrity and ensure traditions are not lost or misrepresented”.
<p>Community (local) Government representative</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Must balance modern needs and community desires with long-term sovereignty and governance. ● Interested in policy, control, and how tech aligns with community values. ● Concerned about data ownership, AI bias, and regulatory frameworks. ● Values inclusiveness and protecting community interests. ● Value Statement: “In my role, I need to weigh all sides and guide the community toward a solution that protects sovereignty and meets people’s needs”.
<p>Tech Developer 1 – Ethics-Oriented</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Believes in responsible AI and ethical development practices. ● Wants to build something meaningful and culturally aligned. ● Understands the power of design decisions and long-term impacts. ● May push back against shortcuts or harmful trade-offs. ● Value Statement: “In my role, I need to build trust and ensure the technology respects community values”.
<p>Tech Developer 2 – Efficiency-Oriented</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focused on timelines, deliverables, and maximizing performance. ● Less concerned with ethics unless they pose a risk to success. ● Believes compromises are necessary for innovation and scaling. ● Wants a clear vision and minimal obstacles to move forward. ● Value Statement: “In my role, I need to push for fast, efficient implementation—even if it means making tough calls”.

Table 1. Participants at the co-design sessions and their interests and values

Examples of some of the questions on which design teams should make joint decisions are shown in the table below, based on following criteria:

- **Efficiency** – Speed, functionality, and ease of implementation
- **Accountability** – Oversight, transparency, and ethical safeguards
- **Community Trust** – Alignment with community values, culture, and participation

1. Oversight & Decision-Making

Who oversees the design and development of the AI system?

Option	Trust	Notes		
A. Tech team works independently	✓✓✓	✗✗	✗✗	Fast, but lacks cultural grounding and accountability
B. Community-led oversight council	✗✗✗	✓✓	✓✓✓	Deeply respectful, but extremely slow to implement
C. One-time community consultation during design	✓	✓	✗	Looks inclusive, but excludes long-term input and oversight

2. Data Collection

How will you train your AI system?

Option	Trust	Notes		
A. Use all existing recordings without restriction	✓✓✓	✗✗	✗✗	Fast, but includes sacred or private content without consent
B. Curate a dataset with extensive community review	✗✗✗	✓✓	✓✓	Slower, but respects protocol and community control

C. Let individuals opt-in with their own stories	✗	✓	✓	Transparent and empowering, but yields less usable data
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3. Data Storage & Sovereignty

Where will your AI system and language data live?

Option	Trust	Notes		
A. Commercial cloud storage (AWS, Google)	✓✓✓	✗✗✗	✗✗	Cheap and fast, but community has no control or security guarantees
B. Local servers, locally maintained	✗✗✗	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Most sovereign, but highest cost and technical burden
C. Hybrid (external provider + local backup)	✓✓	✗	✓	More control than cloud, but external dependence remains

4. Ownership & Licensing

Who owns and controls the final system?

Option	Trust	Notes		
A. Developer owns it under license	✓✓	✗✗	✗	Easy legal process, but no community control over future use
B. Community owns all code and datasets	✗✗	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	Most control, but limits outside partnerships and adds cost

C. Shared co-ownership with advisory board	✓	✓	✗✗	Collaborative on paper, but can lead to confusion and distrust
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5. Long-Term Governance

Who will manage the system after it launches?

Option	Trust	Notes		
A. Hand over to Community Council	●	✓	✓✓	Adds workload to governance, but ensures local oversight
B. Community-managed language tech team	✗	✓✓	✓✓✓	Builds capacity and trust, but hard to sustain without funding
C. External dev team provides ongoing updates	✓✓	✗✗	✗✗	Efficient but gives up local control and accountability

After the stakeholders’ meeting session, project team will need to fill in the following project tracking sheet with joint results:

Design Decisions

Decision #	Choice Made (A/B/C)	Efficiency	Accountability	Community Trust
1				
2				
3				
Total	--			

Based on the total scores on three categories, the following possible tech design options can emerge in the Community-Led Innovation Projects:

Highest Category	Lowest Category	Outcome Profile	Description
 Trust	Fast but Fragile System	Quick deployment but lacking deep community connection.	
 Accountability	Technically Sound but Alienating	Efficient, but lacking governance and connection with those it serves.	
 Efficiency	Culturally- Rooted but Slow to Launch	Strong community oversight but harder to deliver quickly.	
 Trust	Protected Legacy System	Carefully built, but public buy-in is limited.	
 Efficiency	Beloved but Limited Tool	Deep trust but slow progress and small scale.	
 Accountability	Community First, Governance Struggles	Loved by users but lacks strong long-term structures.	
Balanced (No highs or lows)	-	Sustainable and Inclusive Technology	Balanced speed, accountability, and trust—strong, resilient system.
Negative in All Categories	-	Disconnected Innovation	Fast or slow, ethical or not—it missed the community entirely.

Table 2. Type of tech systems developed in civil tech based on values of efficiency, accountability and trust.

Documentation based on the above questions and tables should be included in the technological innovation projects like CommuniCity. Records in the form of photo and textual documentation of meetings among communities, tech developers, funders and city administration should be publicly available.

CommuniCity

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